

Assessment and Feedback: Student Template

Student ID Number(s): 2433459

Programme: Master of Business Administration -MBA

Module: Dissertation

Dissertation/Extended Essay Supervisor: Daniel Chicksand

Assignment Title: A REVERSE SUPPLY CHAIN NETWORK FOR RECYCLING PHOTOVOLTAIC PANELS IN THE US

Date and Time of Submission: 17/08/2024, 9:00 am CST

Actual Word Count: 11.937

Extension: N **Extension Due Date:**

Grade: 85/100

Please ensure that you complete and attach this template to the front of all work that is submitted.

Declaration

By submitting your work, you are certifying that the submission is the result of your own work and does not contravene the University Code of Practice on Academic Integrity^{1,2}. You must ensure that you have referred to valid sources of information to support your work, and that these are properly referenced in the required format (i.e. using Harvard referencing style).

If you have used a proofreader to review all or part of your work, you must declare this here:

I have not used a proofreader

I acknowledge the use of a proofreader. I confirm that the proofreader has not edited the text in an unacceptable manner as specified in Section A.1.6 of the Code of Practice on Academic Integrity² and School guidance.

If you have used Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) to support the development of all or part of your work, you must declare this here:

No content generated by GenAI tools has been used in the development of my final submission.

I acknowledge the use of GenAI in my final submission and confirm this has not been included as my own work. I have carefully checked and appropriately used the output according to the University's guidance on using Generative Artificial Intelligence tools ethically for study³ and I take full responsibility of the entirety of the final

¹ <https://intranet.birmingham.ac.uk/student/academic-support/academic-integrity-support-and-advice.aspx>

² <https://intranet.birmingham.ac.uk/as/registry/legislation/codesofpractice/index.aspx>

³ <https://intranet.birmingham.ac.uk/as/libraryservices/asc/student-guidance-gai.aspx>

submission. *If this option has been selected, please retain your outputs as these could be requested by the module leader grading your work.*

The purpose of this template is to ensure you receive targeted feedback that will support your learning. It is a requirement to complete to complete all 3 sections, and to include this completed template as the first page of every assignment that is submitted for marking (your School will advise on exceptions).

Section One: Reflecting on the feedback that I have received on previous assessments, the following issues/topics have been identified as areas for improvement: (add 3 bullet points). *NB – for first year students/PGTs in the first term, this refers to assessments in your previous institution*

- Utilize quantitative data.
- Reference papers from academic journals.
- Connect the discussion with the literature review.

Section Two: In this assignment, I have attempted to act on previous feedback in the following ways (3 bullet points)

- Gather secondary data to substantiate my analysis.
- Utilize peer-reviewed academic papers as references.
- Provide a complete and connected study throughout the sections in it.

Section Three: Feedback on the following aspects of this assignment (i.e. content/style/approach) would be particularly helpful to me: (3 bullet points)

- Appropriateness of the theoretical framework applied to the case.
- What other qualitative and quantitative elements could be included in the analysis to make it more robust.
- What other frameworks could be applied to the case.

Contents

Chapter 1. Introduction	5
Chapter 2. Literature Review	7
2.1. Industrial Ecology	7
2.2. Green Supply Chain Management	7
2.3. Circular Economy	8
2.4. Convergences and divergences of CE and GSCM	9
2.5. A general framework of SCM and CE and future research fields	11
2.6. State of the art of GSCM and CE in the Photovoltaic industry	13
2.7. Current challenges of CE and GSCM in PV panels	15
2.8. Aim of the study	17
Chapter 3. Methodology	18
3.1. Ontology and Epistemology	18
3.2. Theoretical Framework	18
3.3. Characterization and growth estimations	19
3.3.1. Data Collection	19
3.3.2. Growth estimation models	20
3.4. Waste Forecasting and Composition	20
3.5. PV Recycling centres location and Operational Allocation	21
3.5.1. Decision Variables	22
3.5.2. Parameters	22
3.5.3. Optimization model	23
3.5.4. Model Calibration	24
Chapter 4. Findings	27
4.1. Characterization and growth estimations	27
4.1.1. Randomness analysis	27
4.1.2. MW generation forecast	28
4.2. Waste forecasting and composition	31
4.2.1. Technology market share and Weight-to-power forecasting	31
4.2.2. Waste forecasting	32
4.3. Location and operational allocation	34
4.3.1. Location Optimization	34
4.3.2. Scenario analysis	35

4.3.3. Operational allocation	39
Chapter 5. Discussion	40
5.1. Contributions.....	40
5.3. Limitations	41
5.4. Future direction	42
Chapter 6. Conclusions	44
Glosary of acronyms	46
Appendix	47
Appendix 1. – Weight-to-power ratio of different PV technologies.	47
Appendix 2. – PV technology Market share forecast.....	48
Appendix 3. – Solar energy production forecast by state (MW).....	50
Appendix 4.-Weighted average of weight-to-power ratio.....	51
Appendix 5. – Latitude and Longitude of optimum locations per scenario	52
References:	53

Chapter 1. Introduction

The growing issue of waste generated by photovoltaic (PV) panels at the end of their life cycle is the central concern of this dissertation. As the adoption of solar energy continues to expand, the inevitable consequence is the accumulation of solar panel waste, projected to reach 80 million tonnes globally by the year 2050 (Weckend et al, 2016). Without proper management, this waste is destined for landfills, posing significant environmental and health risks. This paper seeks to address the critical need for effective recycling strategies to mitigate the impending waste management crisis in the solar energy industry by designing an optimal reverse supply chain (RSC) network.

Previous research has laid a substantial foundation in understanding the complexities of end-of-life (EOL) management for photovoltaic panels. Studies have proposed various business models aimed at closing the loop on solar panel waste, including the identification of EOL types, the timing for material reintegration into the supply chain, and the selection of reprocessing methods. Additionally, the rapid evolution of technology suggests that by the time PV modules reach their EOL, they may be obsolete, necessitating different management principles beyond recycling. The literature also explores the diverse processes required to reintroduce PV materials into the supply chain, ranging from mechanical to chemical treatments. However, economic feasibility remains a concern, with studies indicating that the net present value of recycling PV is negative for smaller facilities, and the cost-effectiveness of recycling is often overshadowed by the cheaper alternative of landfill disposal. Furthermore, the design of supply chain networks through mathematical optimization models has shown promise in enhancing cost performance, although such models have not been extensively applied across the United States.

Despite the progress made in prior research, there remain significant gaps that this dissertation aims to address. The concept of circular design, which prioritizes recyclability in the material design of PV panels, has not been sufficiently prioritized, leading to a lack of standardization that complicates recycling efforts. Collaboration among supply chain stakeholders has been identified as crucial for the success of a circular supply chain, yet there is a need for more concerted efforts in this area. Moreover, the strategic positioning of network channels, the management of waste volumes by take-back centres, and the optimization of reverse logistics supply chains, particularly in terms of collection and recycling centre locations, have not been adequately explored. These elements are vital for overcoming the barriers to establishing effective RSC for PV recycling.

This paper is built upon the framework developed by Chiquillo-Molano (2022) for designing RSC networks for PV recycling in the United States. By analyzing historical data to forecast waste generation, an optimization model is employed to determine the optimal locations for Collection Centres (CCs) and Recycling Centres (RCs) that minimize reverse logistics costs. This approach aims to streamline the recycling process, making it more economically viable and environmentally sustainable.

The contributions of this dissertation are multifaceted and significant. It is proposed a data model for forecasting solar panel waste and define an optimization model that proposes a supply chain network that minimizes total costs, including transportation and capital expenses associated with establishing RCs and CCs. By reducing these costs, a more favourable financial outcome is facilitated, which would increase the rate of panel recycling, and decrease overall waste.

The structure of the remainder of this paper is methodically organized to provide a comprehensive analysis of the topic. It begins with a literature review that examines the evolution of Circular Economy (CE) and Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM), applying these concepts to the specific context of solar panel waste management. This review identifies current gaps in the literature and formulates the research questions that guide this study. Following the literature review, the methodology is outlined and followed by the implementation phase, which includes an analysis of historical data in the United States to forecast waste generation, that is later used to optimize the CCs and RCs locations. The paper concludes with a discussion of the findings and their implications for the future of PV recycling.

Chapter 2. Literature Review

The theories that this dissertation will be based on to elucidate strategies for sustainable disposal of solar panels while minimizing environmental impact and promoting resource efficiency will be within the frameworks of Circular Economy (CE) and Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM). By analyzing the origins and existing research of these two fields, the literature review will evaluate the state-of-the-art frameworks applied to managing PV panels at their EOL, the current challenges that it faces, and will outline the research gaps the dissertation will aim to cover.

2.1. Industrial Ecology

One of the earliest works that addressed the effects of industry on the environment from the resources extraction perspective was presented by Ayres & Kneese (1969) where the pollution caused by the flow of materials was described and suggested the possibility of integrating waste materials back into the system. Later seminal research by Frosch and Gallopoulos (1989) elucidated the strategic approach of utilizing waste from products and processes as raw materials for future manufacturing activities, emphasizing the recycling strategy for metals, a practice that spans millennia for Iron utilization and had the potential for varied applications, thus mitigating environmental repercussions considering the finite nature of these resources. Additionally, they acknowledged the challenges associated with recycling other materials, stemming from logistical complexities in classification and appropriate processing techniques. Subsequently, the concept of Industrial Ecology was described, a perspective that perceives industries as an inherent component of ecosystems, and underscores the importance of adopting an approach that models industrial systems within ecological systems (Lowe, 1993).

2.2. Green Supply Chain Management

One of the first approaches to including the Environment within the scope of Supply Chain Management (SCM) was Sarkis (1995), who applied the Industrial Ecology principles to the SCM and reviewed the implementation of the "design for the environment" concept, which considers all environmental consequences of a product, and recognized the importance of focusing on collaboration throughout the SC to reduce the footprint on the environment. Additionally, the 4R principles were formally introduced within the scope of GSCM: Reducing, Recycling, Reusing + Remanufacturing (Sarkis & Rasheed, 1995). Furthermore, it discussed how various operational practices aimed at transitioning towards an Industrial Ecology framework, such as the integration Just-in-Time (JIT) as a way to reduce overproduction, and Total Quality Management (TQM) principles for setting environmentally responsible manufacturing in the design; strategies that have been backed up by more recent studies that validate the enhancement of environmental performance by incorporating JIT and TQM in GSCM (Green et al, 2019a; Agyabeng et al, 2020; Green et al, 2019b; Aityassineet al, 2021; Zaid & Sleimi, 2021; Soltanmohammadi et al, 2021; Jermisittiparsert et al, 2019; Makhlouf et al, 2023).

Later work formalized the concept of GSCM (Beamon, 1999; Narashiman & Carter, 1998) and identified the different environmental problems the SC should aim to reduce: Solid and hazardous waste, Natural resource use, and Water and Air pollution. More recent definitions outline GSCM as the *integration of environmental concerns into the inter-organizational practices of SCM, including product design, material sourcing and selection, manufacturing, delivery of final products, and the management of product's end-of-life* (Srivastava, 2007; Sarkis et al, 2011).

Subsequent studies established the Close Loop Supply Chain Management (CLSCM) concept by applying the principle of reverse flows from customers to manufacturers (Jayaraman et al., 1997). Latest definitions conceptualize CLSCM as a strategic dimension that increases value through the material recovery and collaboration among stakeholders (Sillanpää, 2019; Guide & Van Wassenhove, 2009). Following this, the integration of CLSCM into the realm of GSCM highlighted the observation that the expenses associated with material recovery outweigh those of Eco-Designing products. Consequently, there emerged a consensus on the necessity of integrating Eco-Design principles to make feasible the closure of material loops (Zhu et al, 2006, Van Hoek, 1999; Krikke et al, 2004).

In Srivastava's (2007) literature review on GSCM, he categorized this field's challenges into green design and manufacturing, focusing on disassembly ease, reverse logistics (RL), network design, and waste management, all essential for fostering an effective GSCM. Moreover, he emphasized the ongoing need for a deeper comprehension of RL and its interconnection with the product life cycle. This suggests the necessity of categorizing and selecting the appropriate 4R principle based on the product's life stage, which is in line with other literature reviews that emphasize the importance of assessing the life cycle for improving environmental and social quality (Seurig & Müller, 2008).

As GSCM continues to advance and become integrated into the broader framework of organizational management and economics, there is a growing imperative for additional research that delves into comprehending how stakeholders within the SC can interact or be influenced by both external and internal factors to foster effective collaboration towards environmental benefits (Sarkis et al., 2011).

2.3. Circular Economy

As the concept of GSCM has emerged, there has been a simultaneous increase in environmental involvement in economic studies. This trend emerged from shared foundations with GSCM on Industrial Ecology, by applying its principles to enhance economic performance. Within this context, the concept of CE gained prominence and was in the early 1990s when it was established by Pearce and Turner (1990), where they compared natural systems to productive systems, demonstrating that natural systems operate circularly, while productive systems follow a linear trajectory. Furthermore, the two primary branches of CE were defined, the first one pertains to the flow of materials within

an economy, while the second is focused on analyzing the economic conditions that facilitate such material flows (Elkins et al, 2019).

Subsequently, Kirchherr et al. (2017) analyzed 114 definitions of CE and formulated their definition, establishing CE as *an economic system that is based on business models which replace the 'end-of-life' concept with reducing, alternatively reusing, recycling and recovering materials in production/distribution and consumption processes, thus operating at the micro level (products, companies, consumers), meso level (eco-industrial parks) and macro level (city, region, nation and beyond), with the aim to accomplish sustainable development, which implies creating environmental quality, economic prosperity and social equity, to the benefit of current and future generations.*

CE views industries as a system that is restorative and regenerative by design and aims to keep materials useful and valuable in both biological and technical cycles, where the former can be returned to the environment, while the latter can be recovered and recirculated (Farooque et al, 2019). To achieve this objective, it has been pointed out that the design of circular products needs to be fit for multiple cycles, have long shelf life, and be adaptable to systems changes (Moreno et al, 2016).

In recent years, it has been recognized that CE's focus has been on strategies for keeping technical resources within the economic cycle, while the branch of analyzing the economic conditions that foster circular material flows has not been researched as needed. This leaves behind economic sustainability and the impact of external elements and regulations as facilitators for implementing economically feasible CE principles (Silverio et al., 2023).

After examining the origins and development of GSCM and CE separately, it becomes clear that they share common beginnings, yet have branched into distinct but interconnected disciplines. Consequently, the following section will delineate the similarities and distinctions between these two fields.

2.4. Convergences and divergences of CE and GSCM

Even though both concepts have similar origins and appear to tackle comparable problems, they differ in basic principles and theories and address the problems from different perspectives.

GSCM focuses on integrating environmental thinking into supply-chain management from an end-to-end perspective, from the design of the products until their EOL (Srivastava, 2007). Given that SCM comprises of the administration of flows of products, services, information, and finances, along with the group of entities involved in those administrations (Perez-Franco et al, 2014), the integration of environmental thinking in SCM addresses how the industry can reduce the impact on the environment, while still achieving desired levels of service, costs targets, and supplier-customer relationships. This approach has resulted mainly in optimization and simulation models (Gamboa et al, 2020)

that included environmental constraints within them to achieve optimal solutions for environmental and logistics-cost performance (Yue et al, 2013; You et al, 2011), which may leave aside variables that have a greater impact on economic performance (Liu et al, 2018), would focus only on reducing waste and pollution in a certain fixed amount (Genovese et al, 2017), and would be reliant on the looseness of the environmental restrictions entered into the models.

On the other hand, CE advances the boundaries of environmental sustainability by highlighting the concept of reshaping products to establish viable connections between ecological systems and economic growth, and the ideation of structures that permit self-sustainable production methods where materials could be used indefinitely (Genovese et al, 2017). The applicability of CE has been criticized since the laws of thermodynamics dictate that practicing one of the R principles will always require energy and the infinite recycling of materials without degradation is theoretically impossible (Liening & Bruemmer, 2017), therefore, each implementation resembling a CE must undergo analysis to evaluate its global environmental sustainability impact, as merely achieving a cyclical flow and eco-efficiency does not guarantee a sustainable result (Korhonen et al, 2018). This means that, for a CE system to be sustainable, the cumulative impact of the continuous circulation of materials should not harm the environment and should be regenerative (Genovese et al, 2017), whilst the supporting systems must be maintained stable (Korhonen et al, 2018).

These flaws in both theories can be dealt with through the application of each framework to the other. The reductionism of GSCM through the application of CE, and the idealisms of CE through the flexible restrictions of GSCM models. Such is the case, that the concepts of Reverse Supply Chains (RSCM) (Genovese et al, 2017), Circular Supply Chains (CSCM) (Farooque et al, 2019), or Closed Loop Supply Chains (CLSCM) (Jayaraman et al, 1997) emerged as part of the overlapping of both frameworks or the application of CE in SCM and GSCM, where the focus is to reduce the impact on the environment generated by the industrial activity. Additionally, as part of both fields' convergence, it is worth mentioning the escalation of the R principles, which originated from the 3R framework of Reducing, Reusing, and Recycling, and have expanded to currently encompass the 10R principles of Remanufacturing (Sarkis & Rasheed, 1995), Reconditioning/Refurbishing, Repairing (Rathore et al., 2011), Repurposing/Recontextualizing (den Hollander et al., 2017), Refusing, Rethinking, and Recovering (Bag et al., 2021).

The above shows that despite their distinct approaches, GSCM and CE converge in their commitment to environmental sustainability and the pursuit of a more sustainable future. However, they also exhibit divergence in their scopes and methodologies. While GSCM primarily addresses the operational aspects of SCM in light of ecological performance, CE takes a broader systemic approach that includes the economic conditions that allow materials to be circulated indefinitely in the system.

After examining the points of convergence and divergence between CE and GSCM, the subsequent section will delve into the distinct branches of each discipline, their intersections, and describe future research gaps within this intersection.

2.5. A general framework of SCM and CE and future research fields.

An appropriate way of classifying the different SCM branches is through Elkington’s Tripple Bottom Line which denotes organizational performance as the administration of Economic, Environmental, and Social capital (Gamboa et al, 2020). Therefore, Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM) is an integrative model of GSCM and Social Risk Supply Chain Management (SRSCM) (Gamboa et al, 2020; Cunha et al, 2019), which are built upon the Economic administration through traditional SCM. On the other side, CE has two action lines, the economic conditions that foster circular material flows, and the actual flow of materials (Elkins et al, 2019). The latter overlaps with GSCM and encompasses some of its subfields, such as RSCM, CSCM, and CLSCM.

Figure 1. General framework of GSCM and CE. Adapted from Gamboa et al (2020)

Understanding the convergences between GSCM and CE is important for addressing the appropriate disposal of materials, given that these are the two most widely researched fields for managing waste appropriately. By recognizing where GSCM and CE intersect and the common research gaps, a holistic approach on how to address material disposal can be found, and more impactful outcomes can be achieved.

Within the zone of convergence of both fields, the literature suggests focusing future research on the following key themes.

Research gap	Description	Authors
Design for circularity	Current products are typically disposed of at their EOL, and strategies for designing products that can be recirculated through one of the 10R principles need to be addressed.	Farooque, 2019 Gamboa et al, 2020 Bai et al, 2017 Tanveer et al, 2022 Zahran, 2024 Homrich et al, 2018 Srivastava, 2007 Singh & Trivedi, 2016
Collaboration and coordination between the actors involved in the flow of materials	Fragmented communication and differing priorities among stakeholders, inefficient information sharing, lack of standardized processes, and divergent goals hinder the optimization of circular material flow.	Liu et al, 2018 Farooque, 2019 Gamboa et al, 2020 Korhonen et al, 2018 Zahran, 2024 Plaza-Ubeda et al, 2021 Homrich et al, 2018 Tseng et al, 2019 Srivastava, 2007
Biodegradable packaging and containers	Single-use packaging increases pollution and the capacity demand for circular treatment of materials. Containers that can be returned to the environment would reduce the economic	Liu et al, 2018 Farooque, 2019

	and environmental burden of recirculating materials.	Gamboa et al, 2020
Circular consumption	Overcoming hurdles of today's consumption patterns favouring disposability, limited availability of circular products, and high costs associated with sustainable alternatives, require innovations to promote a shift towards sustainable consumption habits and closed-loop systems.	Farooque, 2019 Gamboa et al, 2020 Sangpech & Ueasangkomsate, 2022
Definition of Physical Flows	There are difficulties in determining the product's life stages at which materials still have economic value and when they become waste.	Farooque, 2019 Korhonen et al, 2018 Plaza-Ubeda et al, 2021 Choi & Fthenakis, 2014
Mathematical optimization models	Optimize green supply chain decisions, such as sourcing, production scheduling, transportation routing, and inventory management, for enhanced sustainability and cost-effectiveness.	Tseng et al, 2019 Kumar & Kant, 2019 Singh & Trivedi, 2016 Fahimnia et al, 2015

Table 3. Future research in the convergence field of GSCM and CE.

Having outlined the future research topics within the intersection of GSCM and CE, their application to solar panels will be discussed in the following section.

2.6. State of the art of GSCM and CE in the Photovoltaic industry

One of the earliest scholarly publications regarding PV recycling was produced by Fthenakis et al (1996) and Fthenakis (2000) who identified that the technology already existed, but the infrastructure was not adapted to recover the materials. After reviewing studies published in the last 10 years, the following key themes of CE and GSCM in the context of solar panels were identified.

An important topic is about the strategies for closing the loop. Several business models have been proposed to recirculate materials, which encompass the identification of different

types of EOL, when to reintegrate materials to the SC, and what manufacturing methods to use for their reprocessing (Hussien et al, 2022; Divya et al, 2015). Furthermore, it has been proposed to prioritize the application of lower-numbered R principles before resorting to higher-numbered ones, which means giving precedence to the Reduction of material usage during the manufacturing of PV, followed by considering Reuse options whenever feasible, and resorting to product repair before considering recycling as the last step (Heath et al, 2022).

Another key theme is regarding PV failure and accelerated EOL. Multiple issues have been identified as causes of PV failure (Vargas & Chesney, 2020), and multiple classifications have been done to understand the value loss of PV and its materials (Chowdhury et al, 2020; Heath et al, 2022; Hussien et al, 2022) to assess when and how to return it to the SC (Heath et al, 2022). Nevertheless, the early loss is only a minor contributor to waste (Divya et al, 2023), and, since the lifespan of a PV module is 25/30 years, by the EOL new technologies would have emerged, making them obsolete to be managed by other principles different than Recycling (Xu et al, 2018), even though it should be one of the last options from the purity of materials perspective (El-Khawad et al, 2022).

Additionally, the technology for CE has been addressed. Given that PVs are composed of different types of materials, the processes for introducing them back to the SC span from mechanical, thermal, and chemical treatments (Corcelli et al, 2018; Shahariar et al, 2020). There have been multiple studies that suggest how to close the loop from the technological point of view, however reinforcing recycling as the principle that adapts better to PVs (Divya et al, 2023).

Furthermore, the economic feasibility of PV panels is one of the most important topics. Gönen & Kaplanoğlu (2019) outline the economic opportunity of recycled materials, as each frame would recover 14,66 USD and by 2050 is projected to have 80MT of waste, equivalent to USD 60 billion. However, this does not consider the financial feasibility that takes into account investments and the value of money over time. Further studies suggest that the NPV of recycling PV is negative for small factories (D'Adamo et al., 2017), as economies of scale for small facilities are not enough to achieve positive NPV (Vargas & Chesney, 2020; El-Khawad et al, 2022). It is also needed that recovered materials are valuable enough to finance the recycling process and that recycled materials are cheaper than virgin ones (El-Khawad et al, 2022), and, given that it currently costs \$15–\$45 to recycle a silicon PV module but only \$1–\$5 to dump it in a landfill (Peplow, 2022), the market incentivizes the disposal rather than the recycling (Franco & Groesser, 2021).

Moreover, the SC network design is also a relevant topic in the PV recycling. Mathematical models have been developed to understand how and where the different nodes should be positioned, and conclude that currently, the optimum scenario is to leverage existing electronic recycling plants to take advantage of economies of scale, as scrap material is not yet sufficient to build dedicated facilities for PV (Vargas & Chesney, 2020; El-Khawad et

al, 2022; Iakovou et al, 2024). Moreover, the optimal positioning of collection Centres has been assessed, concluding that it is more efficient to have centralized and optimally decentralized installations (Acharya et al, 2024). It has also been shown that implementing mathematical optimization models to design the reverse SC network and flows enhances the cost performance and contributes to making the business model economically feasible (Thieu et al, 2022; Molano et al, 2022, Choi & Fthenakis, 2014).

Finally, it has been seen that Circular design and materials management at EOL plays an important role in the discussion. The middle-level 10Rs principles are undesirable, such as Reusing, Remanufacturing, or Repurposing, since technology advances so much within the 25-year PV's lifespan that modules become obsolete, therefore, it is important to consider the 10R options for products early in the design stage (El-Khawad et al, 2022).

Additionally, to have functional materials in the economy, it is needed to keep the purity at maximum levels, thus, mixing at the material, molecular, and atomic levels should be mitigated (El-Khawad et al, 2022), an important issue when using recycled materials for PVs, as containing recycled materials are likely to generate reduced levels of electricity (Franco & Groesser, 2021). Nevertheless, the recirculation of materials doesn't have to be in the same type of products, which would make the recycling of PVs into materials for PVs infeasible due to the purity levels required. Thus, it is needed to consolidate a structure with supportive industries that find recycled materials useful for their value chains and can be utilized for their products with the purity Recycling provides (Heath et al, 2022). Finally, other challenges in the handling of panels at their EOL encompass the presence of heavy metals that can be a threat to health and the environment (Xu et al, 2018), resulting in high dismantling, transportation, and recycling costs required for the special and manual treatment for recycling (Franco & Groesser, 2021).

Even though significant advances have been made in the solar panels' circularity, there are still obstacles that hinder the application of these principles in this sector, which will be discussed next.

2.7. Current challenges of CE and GSCM in PV panels

The particularities of solar panels make them very difficult to dispose of at their EOL, making it economically unfeasible and stimulating owners to dispose of panels in landfills, rather than putting them back into the SC for their materials recirculation. The main roadblocks that are currently impeding the PV panels recycling are listed below.

The first one is regarding Circular Design. To ensure the longevity of solar panels, their structure is based on tightly sealed protection for solar cells with multiple materials and glues that impede the repair, reuse, or recycling (Radavičius et al, 2021). Furthermore, PV panels comprise a variety of materials such as glass, aluminium, silicon, and rare metals, each requiring specific treatment and recycling procedures, thus, giving priority to material design with recyclability in consideration is essential to promote the development of PV panels using materials that are inherently more recyclable (Iakovou, 2024). Additionally,

the lack of standardization of panels creates an additional burden to treatment plants and forces them to manage certain types of modules (Radavičius et al, 2021), which reduces the economies of scale required to turn into an economically feasible recycling business model for PV panels recycling (Vargas & Chesney, 2020).

The second key theme is about Collaboration. It is essential to increase the cooperation between the stakeholders of the SC, given that the effect of multiple strategies downstream or upstream affects the overall behaviour and performance of a CSCM. Aspects such as Reducing the materials in design can result in less valuable materials to be recycled and financial disturbance to recyclers (El-Khawad et al, 2022), an element that could be identified by recyclers, if not communicated on time, decades after the implementation of newer designs, when those enhanced panels get to their domain and could be too late to implement measures to guarantee financial performance. This is why Designing and Forecasting based on collaboration is essential to ensure the long-term sustainability of the Circular Photovoltaic Panels Economy (Mahmoudi et al, 2019). Therefore, by promoting an environment of open data sharing, design collaboration, and feasibility from an end-to-end SC perspective, the stakeholders can collectively contribute to the development of the PV CE (Iakovou et al, 2024).

The final topic is about SC network and Reverse Logistics. The foundation of establishing a sustainable RSC network rests on continuous endeavours to optimize costs across the entire SC spectrum (Iakovou, 2024). To achieve this goal, it is required to address the positioning of network channels, the volume of waste managed by a take-back Centre, and the potential issues stemming from the reverse logistics SC (Mahmoudi et al, 2019), with emphasis on the latter on the cost of collecting materials and the optimal location of recycling and collection Centres, as it is one of the major barriers to establish reverse SC for PV recycling (Tao et al, 2020; Molano, 2022, Choi & Fthenakis, 2014).

Design for Circularity and Collaboration through the SC are inherently intertwined, as they mutually support each other in ensuring that designs incorporate essential criteria for recycling solar panels at their EOL, while also preparing recyclers to manage future designs effectively. Therefore, they can be viewed as a unified approach. Conversely, the challenge of SC Network and RL Centres on effectively managing the material flow to ensure its seamless integration into the SC, regardless of whether designs and collaboration are optimal. Therefore, there are identified two key themes in this field: Design for Circularity and Collaboration, and SC Network and RL.

From the two key challenges identified in the literature review, this dissertation will focus on understanding how the SC Network should be designed to reduce the costs of RL and material recovery. While circular designs are at the forefront of CE research, the economic feasibility of PV recycling is still a challenge, therefore this study will prioritize the logistics costs of positioning recycling plants.

Additionally, this study will focus on the leading geography for projected PV waste. As China, the US, and Japan are anticipated to be at the forefront of this issue (Statista, 2016), the study will concentrate on a single country to minimize the variability of different sources of information between countries. To further simplify and ensure consistency, the dissertation will focus exclusively on the United States and its top 12 states with the highest solar energy production, as they comprise 77% of the total production in the US (SEIA, 2024), thereby eliminating potential language barriers and simplifying the analysis by not considering small clusters that might not impact in a greater certain the results, and that can be adapted to its solutions.

2.8. Aim of the study

The objective is to develop an optimized reverse logistics network within the United States, aimed at significantly reducing SC costs. This strategic approach seeks to enhance the financial viability of panel recycling, thereby contributing to the implementation of recycling value chains and ultimately the reduction of PV waste. By implementing a well-designed reverse logistics framework, the project intends to streamline the collection, transportation, and processing of recyclable panels, ultimately minimizing waste and maximizing resource recovery. Following this, the research questions derived from the literature review are as follows:

1. How should the Supply Chain be set up to minimize the logistics costs of solar panel recycling in the US?
2. Where should the different recycling plants be commissioned to have a cost-effective Supply Chain in the US that attends the top 12 states with the highest solar energy production?
3. What should be the installed capacity of said plants per PV technology and its growth projection?

Chapter 3. Methodology

In this section will be explained the ontology, epistemology, and theoretical framework the dissertation will be based on to answer the research questions, followed by the sources of data and its analysing models for each element of the framework. Finally, a regulatory analysis is performed to evaluate the feasibility, advantages and disadvantages of the locations in the different scenarios proposed.

3.1. Ontology and Epistemology

This study is based on a positivist approach, which emphasizes the use of empirical data and scientific methods to study phenomena (Saunders et al, 2020). The study assumes that there is an objective reality that exists independently of human perception. It also assumes that photovoltaic panels waste is a real and measurable phenomenon that can be studied and predicted, and that the most appropriate approach to deal with it is through recycling.

The ontology of the study assumes that there is a cause-and-effect relationship between the solar energy installed and the resulting waste generated. This study assumes that the optimal RSC network can be objectively designed based on empirical data and mathematical models. This means that it is assumed that the factors that contribute to photovoltaic panels waste can be identified and measured, and that the resulting waste generated can be predicted based on these factors.

The epistemology of the study assumes that knowledge can be obtained through observation, measurement, and experimentation. The study uses quantitative research methods to collect secondary data and analyze it, such as statistical analysis and mathematical modelling. The researcher's role is to remain objective and neutral, and to avoid influencing the research outcomes (Saunders et al, 2020). The study also assumes that the results obtained from the research can be generalized to other contexts, as long as the same methods are used.

3.2. Theoretical Framework

This dissertation utilizes Chiquillo Molano's et al (2022) holistic reverse logistics planning framework for PV recycling to address the research questions on minimizing logistics costs and strategically commissioning recycling plants in the US. The framework's stages guide the research process, ensuring a comprehensive approach to optimizing the SC for solar panel recycling. Only the first three steps will be considered, as they are the ones that address the reverse logistics costs focus of the dissertation. The last two steps involve technology and financial assessments, which would require more in-depth investigation and are out of the scope of this dissertation.

Figure 2. Holistic approach framework (Chiquillo Molano et al, 2022)

3.3. Characterization and growth estimations

This stage identifies major stakeholders in the PV industry, including producers, installers, suppliers, and recyclers. It involves analyzing current and historical data on the installed capacity to identify PV clusters and growth patterns. By examining technologies, market shares, and PV types, this stage estimates system inputs to forecast future growth and identify critical areas for logistic strategy development.

3.3.1. Data Collection

To ensure a comprehensive and accurate analysis, the data on current PV panel installations, production rates, and technological trends will be gathered. This data collection will rely on secondary sources renowned for their reliability and precision. These sources include the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), the Solar Energy Industries Association (SEIA), the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA), and various industry reports. By synthesizing information from these authoritative entities, the project aims to obtain a robust understanding of the current landscape of PV panel

deployment and advancements. This approach will enable the reverse logistics network design to be based on the most current and relevant data, ensuring that strategies are both innovative and grounded in real-world trends and statistics.

3.3.2. Growth estimation models

To analyze trends in energy production using solar technology, the model presented in Figure 3 will be followed. This approach allows for an examination of the data from a broad to a detailed perspective. First, it will be determined whether the data is random using a Runs test by Mean comparison, and fits a probability distribution through a Goodness of Fit analysis. Otherwise, if the data shows regular patterns, trends, or seasonality, the best forecasting method will be identified by comparing linear regression, exponential smoothing, Holt-Winters, and Holt-Winters with trend, selecting the method with the highest coefficient of determination.

Figure 3. Estimation growth models. Source: Author.

3.4. Waste Forecasting and Composition

This stage focuses on estimating the future waste stream from PV panels and its material composition with the purpose of later understanding the different recycling technologies needed and their required capacity. It analyzes main PV technologies, considering market

share and technical specifications. These specifications help determine the composition and material inventory of PV waste. Scenarios based on PV failure rates are modeled to estimate waste generation, which is then broken down into material compositions.

By converting annual installed capacity into mass using the weight-to-power ratio WP , the projected PVs at a certain year t are calculated, as exhibited in equation 1 (Chiquillo Molano et al, 2022). The waste composition of EOL PV panels will be determined to identify the types and quantities of materials that will be available for recycling at certain points in time. This breakdown will be established by disaggregating the waste forecast into the different PV technologies i and their material percentage MP based on their market share MS at year t as shown in equation 3.

To estimate waste generation through time, the data on degradation rates and failure rates will be utilized and modelled using the Weibull function for regular loss scenario, where the probability of a panel failure from its commissioning in year t is calculated, based on the average panel life T and a distribution shape factor α , as described in equation 4 (Chiquillo Molano et al, 2022). Finally, the total amount of panel waste by technology i at year t will be calculated as the difference between the probability of panel failure of technology i in years $t+1$ and t , as shown in equation 5.

$$[1] \text{Panel}_t = P_t = kW_t * WP$$

$$[2] \text{Panel}_{ti} = P_{ti} = P_t * MS_{ti}$$

$$[3] \text{Material}_t = M_t = P_{ti} * MP_i$$

$$[4] \text{Panel failure probability}_t = PF_t = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^\alpha}$$

$$[5] \text{Panel waste}_{it} = PW_{it} = PF_{t+1} * P_{t+1i} - PF_t * P_{ti}$$

3.5. PV Recycling centres location and Operational Allocation

This section outlines the Non-Linear Programming model designed to optimize the location and allocation of collection and recycling centres. The model considers the demand determined in the previous stage, along with various costs associated with transportation, facility commissioning, and operation. The objective is to minimize these costs by selecting the optimal range and locations for collection and recycling facilities.

The model results will provide the minimum total costs, as well as the number and locations of the facilities. Various scenarios will be considered, including configurations with 1 to 4 collection centres and 1 to 3 recycling plants. To be adapted to the optimization model, the geographical coordinates will be treated as continuous variables, spanning from the northernmost, southernmost, easternmost, and westernmost points of the continental United States.

3.5.1. Decision Variables

- y_i : Binary variable, 1 if collection Centre i is opened, 0 otherwise.
- z_j : Binary variable, 1 if recycling plant j is opened, 0 otherwise.
- x_{di} : Amount of demand Q_d from demand point d supplied to collection Centre i .
- w_{ij} : Amount of material transported from collection Centre i to recycling plant j .
- lat_i : Latitude of collection Centre i .
- lon_i : Longitude of collection Centre i .
- lat_j : Latitude of recycling plant j .
- lon_j : Longitude of recycling plant j .

3.5.2. Parameters

- F_i : Fixed cost of opening collection Centre i .
- C_j : Fixed cost of opening recycling plant j .
- T_{di} : Transportation cost per unit distance from demand point d to collection Centre i .
- dd_i : Distance from demand point d to collection Centre i .*
- T_{ij} : Transportation cost per unit distance from collection Centre i to recycling plant j .
- d_{ij} : Distance from collection Centre i to recycling plant j .*
- H_i : Variable handling cost per unit at collection Centre i .
- P_j : Variable processing cost per unit at recycling plant j .
- Q_d : Demand at demand point d .
- NC : Number of collection Centres to be opened.
- NR : Number of recycling plants to be opened.
- M : Large constant for linking constraints.
- $minlat$: Minimum feasible latitude.
- $maxlat$: Maximum feasible latitude.
- $minlon$: Minimum feasible longitude.
- $maxlon$: Maximum feasible longitude.

3.5.3. Optimization model

Minimize

$$\sum_{i \in S} F_i y_i + \sum_{j \in R} C_j Z_j + \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{i \in S} T_{di} d_{di} x_{di} + \sum_{i \in S} \sum_{j \in R} T_{ij} d_{ij} w_{ij} + \sum_{i \in S} \sum_{d \in D} H_i x_{di} + \sum_{j \in R} \sum_{i \in S} P_j w_{ij}$$

Subject to

$\sum_{i \in S} y_i = N_c$	—————>	Number of Collection Centres
$\sum_{j \in R} Z_j = N_R$	—————>	Number of Recycling Plants
$\sum_{i \in S} x_{di} = Q_d$	$\forall d \in D$ ———>	Demand Satisfaction
$\sum_{j \in R} w_{ij} - \sum_{d \in D} x_{di} = 0$	$\forall i \in S$ ———>	Flow Conservation in collection centres
$\sum_{d \in D} x_{di} - M y_i = 0$	$\forall i \in S$ ———>	Linking constraint for collection centres
$\sum_{i \in S} w_{ij} - M z_j = 0$	$\forall j \in R$ ———>	Linking Constraint for Recycling Plants
$y_i \in \{0,1\}$	$\forall i \in S$ ———>	Binary Constraints
$Z_j \in \{0,1\}$	$\forall j \in R$ ———>	
$x_{di} \geq 0$	$\forall d \in D, \forall i \in S$ ———>	Non-Negativity Constraints
$w_{ij} \geq 0$	$\forall j \in R, \forall i \in S$ ———>	
$Lat_i \in [\min lat, \max lat]$	$\forall i \in S$ ———>	Location Constraints
$Lat_j \in [\min lat, \max lat]$	$\forall j \in R$ ———>	
$Lon_i \in [\min lon, \max lon]$	$\forall i \in S$ ———>	
$Lon_j \in [\min lon, \max lon]$	$\forall j \in R$ ———>	

*The distance between two points will be calculated as equation 6 and entered into the objective function.

$$[6] d_{ij} = \text{acos} \sqrt{\sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta_{lat}}{2}\right) + \cos(lat_i) * \cos(lat_j) * \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta_{lon}}{2}\right)} * 2 * 6371$$

3.5.4. Model Calibration

This methodology requires the input of several key parameters into the models to initialize them quantitatively and enable the projection of waste volumes per state and the determination of optimal recycling locations.

For growth estimations, the parameters entered into the exponential smoothing model are shown in Table 4. The data smoothing factor is set to 1, as the forecast for year $i+1$ will be based on the capacity of year i . The trend smoothing factor will be chosen based on which value increases the correlation coefficient the most, which is 0. the growth rate of solar energy production is anticipated to decelerate, as perpetual increases are unsustainable. To account for this expected shift, a deceleration factor, denoted as λ , will be incorporated into the model to accurately represent this change in momentum (EIA, 2023).

Parameter	Description	Value	Units	Sources
α	Smoothing factor	1	-	
β	Trend smoothing factor	0	-	
λ	Factor after 2030	0.5	-	EIA, 2023

Table 4. Growth estimation parameters – exponential smoothing.

The parameters entered into the model are shown in Table 5 for the waste forecasting and composition. The weight-to-power ratio will be entered based on the weighted average of the forecasted market share per technology, as shown in Appendixes 1 and 2. For the panel failure probability and average lifetime, various studies that evaluate the PV panels' EOL consider the report from the International Renewable Energy Agency as their reference (Mahmoudi et al, 2021; Santos & Alonso-Garcia, 2021; Sharma et al, 2023; Gautam et al, 2021; Lee & Jang, 2023). This study will follow this line and consider the T value as 30 years and the α distribution shape as 5.3759 for the regular-loss scenario (Weckend et al, 2016).

Parameter	Description	Value	Units	Sources
WP	Weight-to-power ratio	Variable (Appendix 1)	Kg/W	Chiquillo-Molano
MS	Technology Market share per year	Variable (Appendix 2)	%	Weckend et al, 2016
α	Panel Failure probability	5.3759		Weckend et al, 2016
T	Average lifetime	30	Years	Weckend et al, 2016

Table 5. Waste forecasting parameters.

Regarding the location optimization model, the parameters will be based on table 6. The Fixed cost of opening collection centre will be assumed to be 10% of the fixed cost of opening a recycling plant, as the main cost of RC commissioning is the technology required, rather than the physical space (Vargas & Chesney, 2020).

Parameter	Description	Value	Units	Sources
F	Fixed cost of opening collection Centre	10,475,190	\$	Vargas & Chesney, 2020
C	Fixed cost of opening recycling plant	104,751,900	\$	Vargas & Chesney, 2020
T	Transportation cost	0.0000604	\$/Kg*K m	scale funding, 2024
H	Variable handling cost per unit at collection Centres	0.1	\$/Kg	Vargas & Chesney, 2020
P	Variable processing cost per unit at recycling plants	441.24	\$/Ton	D'Adamo et al, 2017
Q	Demand per region	Variable, based on forecast	Kg	Seia, 2024
NC	Number of collection Centres to be opened	{1,2,3,4}	-	
NR	Number of Recycling Centres to be opened	{1,2,3,4}	-	
M	Large constant	999999999	-	
MinLat	Minimum feasible latitude	24.396308	degrees	COPH, nd
MaxLat	Maximum feasible latitude	49.384358	degrees	COPH, nd
MinLon	Minimum feasible longitude	66.949895	degrees	COPH, nd
MaxLon	Maximum feasible longitude	124.733174	degrees	COPH, nd

Table 6. Location optimization parameters.

The methodology section has delineated the framework for the creation of an optimal RSC network, which is specifically designed for the recycling of solar panels as outlined by Chiquillo-Molano et al (2022). Through the definition of the data analysis and location optimization model, as well as the selection and input of pertinent parameters, the foundation has been laid for the reduction of reverse logistics costs, which in turn enhances the financial viability of the solar panel recycling business model. The methodologies adopted will provide insights into the strategic placement of facilities and the efficient routing of materials, ensuring that the network operates efficiently.

With the groundwork for the RSC now established, the focus shifts to the findings section. Here, the results of applying the model will be presented, and the practical implications of the research will be discussed, particularly in the context of solar panel recycling within the United States. This forthcoming section aims to bridge the gap between theoretical modelling and practical application, highlighting the real-world benefits of implementing an efficient RSC for solar panel recycling.

Chapter 4. Findings

This section will present a review of the analysis results, which aimed to determine the optimal RSC network for PV panel waste management. The methodology followed the comprehensive framework established by Chiquillo-Molano (2022) and was structured into several critical phases: characterization and growth estimation, waste forecasting and composition, and the strategic location and operational allocation of facilities. The outcome of this analysis will identify the most efficient locations for collection Centres (CCs) and recycling centres (RCs) that will service the top 12 solar panel waste-producing states in the United States.

4.1. Characterization and growth estimations

This segment delves into the historical data of solar energy production to project future generation trends. These projections are subsequently utilized to anticipate waste management needs, as detailed in Section 4.2. The analytical process, outlined in Figure 3, commences with randomness tests to assess whether the data exhibits random behaviour. Based on the outcomes of these tests, the analysis proceeds with either a goodness of fit evaluation or a time series forecast to model future scenarios accurately.

4.1.1. Randomness analysis

The MW production data per state over the last 13 years (Appendix 3) was entered into SPSS to conduct a runs test by means. The objective was to determine whether the order of the observations is random or if there is a discernible pattern. In this test, the null hypothesis posits that the sample is random.

As shown in Table 7, the results indicate that all 12 states considered have a p-value of 0.005 or lower. This implies that with a probability of 99.5% or higher, the null hypothesis can be rejected, leading to the conclusion that the values are not random and follow a pattern, thus, the forecast should be based on a time-series analysis.

	Test Value	Cases < Test Value	Cases >= Test Value	Total Cases	Number of Runs	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Arizona	3688.3	7	6	13	2	-2.893	0.004
California	18933.1	8	7	15	2	-3.213	0.001
Colorado	1336.1	8	5	13	2	-2.863	0.004
Florida	3868.9	9	4	13	2	-2.790	0.005
Massachusetts	2062.8	7	6	13	2	-2.893	0.004
Georgia	1977.2	8	5	13	2	-2.863	0.004
New Jersey	2571.9	7	6	13	2	-2.893	0.004

Nevada	2707.8	7	6	13	2	-2.893	0.004
New York	1722.7	9	4	13	2	-2.790	0.005
Texas	6383.1	9	4	13	2	-2.790	0.005
North Carolina	4100.1	7	6	13	2	-2.893	0.004
Virginia	1409.5	9	4	13	2	-2.790	0.005

Table 7. Runs test by means – Solar energy production per state.

This aligns with findings from industry reports (SEIA, 2024; Wackend et al., 2017) that indicate a consistent annual growth in solar energy production across the United States. This upward trend is attributed to the establishment of new solar facilities and the expansion of installed capacity. However, it's important to note that these developments are influenced by the unique characteristics of individual states, suggesting that the increase in solar energy production is a state-specific phenomenon rather than a uniform national trend, as 12 out of the 50 states produce around 77% of the solar energy in the country (SEIA, 2024); therefore, the generation forecast should be analyzed individually per state, which will be addressed in the next section.

4.1.2. MW generation forecast.

By 2023, the United States has reached solar energy production of 200 GW of capacity. The top 12 states for solar production are the powerhouse behind this growth, collectively accounting for 155 GW. Figure 4 captures the evolution of these states' solar capacities, highlighting their significant contributions and the upward trajectory of solar energy's role in the national energy landscape.

Figure 4. MW Production per state. Adopted from (SEIA, 2024)

From an energy production standpoint, facilities can be categorized into three distinct clusters according to production quartiles—Q1&2, Q3 and Q4—as detailed in Table 8. The primary cluster, comprising California, Texas, and Florida, is expected to be the main driver of facility location decisions, being the three states that outstand in capacity, surpassing the 16 GW. The secondary cluster, which encompasses those with capacities between 7 and 10 GW, such as North Carolina, Arizona, and Nevada, is likely to provide supplementary support to the states in the primary cluster, especially those nearby them. The remaining states, with capacities between 4 and 6 GW, are anticipated to align their locations with the patterns established by the first two clusters, adapting to the geographic and recycling dynamics set forth by these leading states.

State	MW	Quartile / Cluster
California	48,482	Q4
Texas	32,142	Q4
Florida	16,640	Q4
North Carolina	9,574	Q3
Arizona	8,487	Q3
Nevada	7,325	Q3
Georgia	5,936	Q1-2
New York	5,834	Q1-2
Virginia	5,418	Q1-2
New Jersey	5,362	Q1-2
Massachusetts	5,233	Q1-2
Colorado	4,168	Q1-2

Table 8. Energy production clusters in 2023.

Considering the rising trend in capacity without clear seasonality or linear patterns, exponential smoothing and linear regression emerge as the most suitable forecast methods. Different from the linear regression, exponential smoothing effectively captures the nuances of the increasing trend in energy production, providing a more appropriate forecasting method for this case. This is corroborated by a superior coefficient of correlation across all states, as evidenced in Table 9, indicating its enhanced predictive accuracy for solar energy trends.

State	R ² Exponential smoothing	R ² Linear regression
Arizona	0.98	0.96
California	0.99	0.98
Colorado	0.99	0.83
Florida	0.98	0.76
Georgia	0.97	0.89
Massachusetts	0.99	0.97
Nevada	0.98	0.94
New Jersey	0.99	0.96
New York	0.99	0.82
North Carolina	0.99	0.98
Texas	0.98	0.67
Virginia	0.97	0.78

Table 9. Coefficient of correlation – Exponential smoothing and linear regression.

Projections extending to 2040 are exhibited in Figure 5 and detailed further in Appendix 3. As these forecasts rely on historical data to anticipate future trends (Castellanos, 2008), it is expected that the current energy production clusters will continue to shape facility location strategies up to the forecast horizon of 2040. This suggests a stable influence of these clusters on the geographic distribution of energy production facilities for the foreseeable future.

Figure 5. MW Production forecast per state 2024-2040.

These projections sum up 1.5 TW by 2040 in all US, which is aligned with industry reports that show that the forecasted capacity is between 0.9 and 1.6 TW (EIA, 2021; EIA, 2023). The tendency for the forecasts in this study to skew towards the upper limit can be attributed to the fact that reports only include data up to 2020 and 2022, omitting the significant increase in 2023 that altered the forecasting trend. This deviation is a common characteristic of forecasting, given that shorter horizon forecasts are more accurate than

longer horizon forecasts and they are expected to always be wrong (MIT, 2015); therefore, the projections in this study were considered as valid and were used as the input for the waste forecasting.

4.2. Waste forecasting and composition.

In this section, the forecast from the previous analysis is utilized to ascertain the volume of waste generated annually. This is achieved by projecting the market share of different PV panel types and converting this information into the associated weight based on their power generation capacity. Following this, the waste forecast is determined by calculating the annual failure probability, using the Weibull distribution model for PV panels. This systematic approach provides a detailed insight into the expected waste generation trends over time.

4.2.1. Technology market share and Weight-to-power forecasting.

Various technologies exhibit unique weight-to-power ratios, detailed in Appendix 1, indicating that waste generation is contingent upon the annual percentage distribution per PV type. To estimate the market share of each technology, data from Weckend et al. (2016) were interpolated and extrapolated, revealing a pattern in technological adoption over time, as illustrated in Figure 6. A shift from older, less efficient technologies to newer ones is anticipated. Silicon-based and Cadmium Telluride (CdTe) PVs are projected to see a significant decline, while Concentrating Solar PVs are likely to become obsolete in the near term. On the other hand, Organic PVs (OPV), Crystalline-Silicon based, Copper Indium Gallium Selenide (CIGS), and other emerging technologies are set to take the lead as the predominant sources of solar energy.

Figure 6. Market share forecast per technology.

Exploring the changing market shares of various PV types provides insight into the potential impact of solar technology advancements on waste generation within the industry. However, projections of waste weight do not show significant fluctuations due to the mix of technologies, as the pro-rated weight-to-power ratio varies only marginally, ranging from 0.10815 to 0.109583 Kg/W in specific years, a mere 1.3% variation, as shown in Appendix 4. This suggests that, over the next 15 years, the costs associated with reverse logistics in the solar industry are unlikely to be significantly affected by shifts in PV technology, but probably impacted by the total energy production.

4.2.2. Waste forecasting.

Given that solar panels installed in a particular year will not all be decommissioned simultaneously or at a uniform rate, it is essential to assess the potential PV waste stream over time. This section will address the probabilistic evaluation of PV panel waste, from the point of installation up to a specified year, to provide a more accurate understanding of the decommissioning timeline and waste generation through time.

Taking into account the annual installed capacity, which is determined by the difference in capacity between consecutive years (year $i+1$ and year i), and applying the weighted average weight-to-power ratio for each year, the annual PV installation is calculated. This process is followed by including the failure probability for each installation year, beginning with the base year ($i=0$), as depicted in Figure 7. The result of this is the waste generated per year.

Figure 7. Weibull distribution for PV panels failure per year.

The findings indicate that the top 12 solar-producing states in the US are expected to generate a cumulative total of 3.6 million tonnes of waste by 2040. This figure significantly exceeds the projections of 1.3 million tonnes reported by IRENA (Weckend et al, 2016). The discrepancy can be attributed to the fact that the IRENA projections were based on EIA data from 2013, which did not account for the substantial rise in PV installations over the last decade. This surge in installations has shifted the growth trend upwards, leading to an increased projection of waste accumulation.

Cumulative waste forecast

Figure 9. Cumulative waste forecast – Top 12 states in the US.

The optimization of facility locations was based by the projected cumulative PV waste by 2040, as depicted in Figure 8 and Table 10. California and Texas, generating the most waste, are expected to exert a strong influence on the facilities location. Notably, the bulk of PV waste is anticipated to be concentrated in coastal states, with Nevada and Colorado being the only inland states of significant waste generation. This is despite the fact that states such as Utah, Kansas, Oklahoma, Louisiana, Mississippi, Alabama, and South Carolina receive more solar radiation than some high solar energy-producing northeastern states, showing that, even though there are states that have strategic advantages from the natural resources perspective, there are other factors that have a greater drive on the solar energy production and the installation of PV panels, such as policy, infrastructure, or economic incentives.

Figure 10. Cumulative waste distribution until 2040

State	Waste (Tons)	Percentage
California	1,430,145	39%
Texas	484,551	13%
Florida	275,260	8%
North Carolina	260,561	7%
Arizona	250,178	7%
Nevada	182,117	5%
New Jersey	172,657	5%
Massachusetts	136,169	4%
Georgia	128,959	4%
New York	118,277	3%
Virginia	93,918	3%
Colorado	93,021	3%
Total	3,625,814	100%

Table 10. Cumulative waste distribution until 2040

Having calculated the forecasted waste, this served as input for designing the optimum RSC, including the number of CCs and RCs and their locations, which will be addressed in the following section.

4.3. Location and operational allocation

This section details the identification of the optimal RSC configuration. By inputting various arrangements ranging from 1 to 4 Collection Centres (CCs) and 1 to 4 Recycling Centres (RCs) into the model, the most advantageous locations for these facilities are determined. Additionally, a comprehensive cost scenario analysis is presented to evaluate the financial implications of each potential network setup.

4.3.1. Location Optimization

The states identified as optimal for hosting these collection and recycling centres are listed in Table 11. For detailed reference, Appendix 5 provides the coordinates for each of the proposed locations. In instances where a RC and a CC are situated within the same state, these facilities would function dually as both RC and CC. This consolidation is strategically designed to minimize logistics costs by streamlining operations within a single location.

Scenario	Facilities	RC	CC
1	1 RC & CC	Arizona	-
2	2 RC & CC	California, North Carolina	-
3	3 RC & CC	California, New Mexico, North Carolina	-
4	4 RC & CC	New Jersey, South Carolina, Texas, California	-
5	1 RC - 2 CC	California	California, North Carolina
6	1 RC - 3 CC	New Mexico	California, New Mexico, North Carolina
7	1 RC - 4 CC	California	New Jersey, South Carolina, Texas, California
8	2 RC - 3 CC	California, Georgia	California, New York, Georgia
9	2 RC - 4 CC	California, North Carolina	New Jersey, South Carolina, Texas, California
10	3 RC - 4 CC	California, North Carolina, Texas	New Jersey, South Carolina, Texas, California

Table 11. Optimum locations.

California features prominently in all modelled scenarios, except for the single-facility network, underscoring the state's significant projected waste volume. This indicates that California's output will have a more substantial influence on the location decisions for new installations compared to other states. Furthermore, for each of these potential configurations, both logistics and capital costs fluctuate based on the volume of material transported and the number of facilities to be established. Consequently, it is essential to evaluate the scenarios to determine the one that yields the lowest total costs, thereby identifying the most cost-effective logistics network. This analysis will be conducted in the subsequent section.

4.3.2. Scenario analysis

Each logistics configuration assessed in the scenarios presents a unique balance of logistics and capital costs. It is observed that as the number of facilities increases, logistics costs tend to decrease due to improved proximity to waste sources, while capital costs rise due to the expenses associated with establishing and operating additional sites. Therefore, the strategic decision on how many facilities to commission and where to place them has an intrinsic trade-off between how close the facilities are to the collection points, and the number of installations to be built.

Figure 11. Scenarios capital and logistics costs.

As depicted in Figure 11, the optimal configuration consists of two RCs and two CCs, with the next best scenarios being two RCs with three CCs, and two RCs with four CCs, respectively. This optimal arrangement is primarily due to the significant decrease in logistics costs achieved by having two RCs strategically located near demand points, as opposed to just one. The addition of a third or fourth RC does not proportionally reduce logistics costs, while it substantially increases capital expenditures, rendering these options less cost-effective.

The rationale behind this is rooted in the expansive geography of the United States, which stretches broadly from west to east, but not as much from south to north, and the distribution of waste generation points, 53% in the western states 13% in the central region, and 34% in the eastern states; while 88% of waste is located in the southern states and only 12% in the northeastern ones. Consequently, establishing two RCs, one in the east and one in the west, significantly reduces logistics costs compared to a single centralized location, and adding another RC in the northeast does not offer the same degree of cost savings as the initial expansion from one to two RCs.

This evaluation operates under the premise that there is no minimum distance requirement between the collection demand in the different states and the nearest CC. Should such a distance constraint exist, it would necessitate an increase in the number of CCs, which could alter the cost-effectiveness of the network. This level of analysis, which would consider minimum distance requirements, falls outside the scope of the current study, and remains to be conducted.

Figure 12. Optimum network - Scenario 2 - 2 RCs & CC network.

In the following most efficient scenarios, the introduction of additional CCs would be necessary. However, the logistics cost savings are not greater than the capital costs associated with establishing new facilities due to the triangulation routing that involves multiple points, State to CC to RC, rather than direct routes from the states to the RCs. Although the model indicates that having two RCs is more efficient, incorporating an additional CC raises costs only by 6%. This adjustment would also shift the location of the eastern RC from North Carolina to Georgia. Such a move positions the RC more strategically in relation to Texas and Florida, states anticipated to generate significant waste, thereby enhancing the SC's adaptability for these areas. Moreover, the placement of a CC in the northeast offers the flexibility for potential relocation or even conversion into an RC in the future, given that the warehousing does not entail the substantial capital investments required for the technology in RCs.

Figure 13. Second most efficient network - Scenario 8. 2 RCs & CC + 1 CC network.

Texas is a pivotal state in determining the optimal network design due to its significant projected waste contribution of 13% and its central geographic location within the United States. As such, the allocation of collection centres in the network scenarios is influenced by Texas' position. However, its impact is primarily on the placement of the eastern facility, as the western facility is consistently located in California across all scenarios, a decision driven by California's substantial 39% share of waste generation.

In the optimum scenario (2 RCs & CC), if Texas is grouped with the eastern states, the recycling centre would potentially shift to South Carolina. While this may reduce logistics costs for Texas, Georgia, and Florida, it would conversely increase costs at a greater amount for Virginia, New York, New Jersey, and Massachusetts. Therefore, it is more efficient to align Texas with the California location.

Figure 13 reveals that in the scenario ranking second in efficiency, the introduction of an additional CC in the northeast justifies allocating Texas to the Eastern RC. As a result, situating the RC in Georgia and adding a collection centre in the northeast emerges as a more prudent strategy than incurring in the capital expenditure required to establish an RC in Texas, which does not present a cost-effective solution. This configuration remains optimal unless solar energy production intensifies in the states surrounding Texas, potentially leading to a centralized solar industry cluster. Should such growth materialize, it could create the economies of scale that would make the investment in a new RC in Texas feasible.

Consequently, given the pivotal role Texas plays, it is advisable to assess the first two scenarios using additional criteria beyond purely mathematical location optimization to determine the most appropriate reverse network configuration. With this in mind, the operational allocation for these two leading scenarios will be presented the subsequent section.

4.3.3. Operational allocation

The analysis of the two most efficient scenarios includes a detailed demand allocation for the various facilities, as well as the necessary capacity at each facility to manage the waste projected through 2040, and the annual capacity requirements from 2040 onwards, as outlined in Table 12.

In Scenario 2, which involves 2 RCs and CCs, it is feasible to commission the facilities and initiate operations by 2035. This would allow for the distribution of the 2.44 million tonnes of waste into an annual recycling throughput of 484 thousand and 238 thousand tonnes, aligning with the projected annual capacity needed from 2040 onwards.

Similarly, for Scenario 8, which proposes 2 RCs and CCs + 1 CC, beginning recycling operations in 2035 is viable. The facilities would process 392 thousand and 334 thousand tonnes annually, respectively, achieving a similar capacity balance for the years extending beyond 2040.

Scenario	Facilities	RC & CC location	States demand allocation	Capacity up to 2040 (Tonnes)	Yearly capacity from 2040 (Tonnes)
2	2 RC & CC	California	California, Nevada, Arizona, Colorado, Texas	2.44 Million	484 Thousand
		North Carolina	Florida, Georgia, North Carolina, Virginia, New Jersey, New York, Massachusetts	1.19 Million	248 Thousand
8	2 RC & CC	California	California, Nevada, Arizona, Colorado	1.96 Million	365 Thousand
		Georgia	Florida, Georgia, North Carolina, Virginia, New Jersey, New York, Massachusetts, Texas	1.67 Million	367 Thousand
	1 CC	New York	New Jersey, New York, Massachusetts,	427 Thousand	81 Thousand

Table 12. Operational allocation and required capacity -Scenario 2 and 8.

Chapter 5. Discussion

After analyzing the solar energy production forecast in the US and its waste projection, an optimal reverse logistics network for PV recycling was determined using Chiquillo-Molano's (2022) framework for solar panel recycling location. The following sections will present a critical review of the results obtained, including their contributions, limitations, and future research directions.

5.1. Contributions

This study focuses on analyzing the optimal locations for setting up a reverse SC in the US to minimize logistics costs. This element addresses several challenges when viewing PV recycling from a holistic perspective, including the economic feasibility of recycling. If panel recycling were to become a more economical alternative for waste generators, and if recycling plants could achieve financial benefits for investors through increased efficiency and reduced costs, it would likely result in the development of a new PV recycling industry that would organically resolve the waste problem. However, it has been determined that one of the biggest obstacles that hinder the PV recyclability is the greater costs compared to their disposal in landfills (Peplow, 2022; Franco & Groesser, 2021); where logistics costs are one of those that have one of the greatest impacts (Iakovou, 2024; Tao et al, 2020; Molano, 2022, Choi & Fthenakis, 2014). Thus, defining a SC where the suggested locations provide the lowest total costs, composed of transportation and capital costs of commissioning RCs and CCs, contribute to reducing the expenses associated to the PV recycling, which ultimately leads to a better financial outcome, increased panel recycling, and waste reduction.

Additionally, this study presents a SC network for closing the loop in the US, which defines centralized points for the return of PV waste for material recovery within the country and put it back in the economy. This contribution aligns with gaps identified in the literature (Heath et al, 2022; Divya et al, 2023; Xu et al, 2018) and enhances the overall business model by reducing uncertainty and eliminating extra steps that would be required to identify optimal facility locations.

Finally, this study served as a test for Chiquillo-Molano's (2022) framework for solar panel recycling location by applying it to a different geography and understanding different elements that could enhance it for better outcomes when applied in the future. It was found that the framework lacked a data analysis model for energy production forecasting based on time series, which was introduced in this study. Additionally, the framework did not include a location optimization model that considers both CCs and RCs, allocates the different collection demand points to each facility, and defines in advance the number of RCs and CCs to be analyzed in the selected geography.

To address these limitations, the study utilized an optimization model that included all the mentioned parameters and variables to have a more accurate outcome. Apart from this, spherical coordinates and distances between two points were included to provide a more accurate estimate of the logistics costs associated with PV recovery in large areas, such as

the United States, where Euclidean distances can introduce errors in the results. The above elements contribute to a more robust mathematical optimization model for better location selection that minimizes transportation costs, which is a current challenge in both GSCM and CE as macro fields of knowledge (Tseng et al, 2019, Kumar & Kant, 2019, Singh & Trivedi, 2016; Fahimnia et al, 2015); as well as in CE and GSCM applications in the material management of solar panels (Thieu et al, 2022; Molano et al, 2022, Choi & Fthenakis, 2014).

Having outlined the way this study strengthens the gaps identified in the literature review, in the next sections will be pointed out its limitations to further comprehend the applicability of the results.

5.3. Limitations

Even when this study contributes to the financial feasibility of PV recycling, strategies for closing the loop, more appropriate mathematical optimization models, and a different geography and context for applying Chiquillo-Molano's (2022) framework, it presents several limitations, both on the way it forecasts energy production and waste, as well as how it defines the optimum locations.

Regarding the energy production forecast, it is based on a time series analysis, which assumes the future behaviour will follow the trends from previous years, however, does not consider the underlying causes of these patterns and ignores how they, along with other upcoming behaviours, shape the future energy production. It has been shown that multivariate models for forecasting solar energy production present lower mean absolute error than univariate ones, such as time-series analysis (Cabello-Lopez et al, 2023), thus, considering not only the time trend, but also the regulations, incentives, economy, culture, technology, among other elements, is necessary for attaining a more accurate energy forecast.

As per the PV waste forecast, two major improvement opportunities arise from the analysis. The first one concerns the PV technology type. It is shown that other alternatives apart from the known ones will grow in the next two decades, and their weight-to-power ratio and composition are unknown, thus, the waste projection has an intrinsic error that could be reduced by performing a technology forecast to comprehend when and what technologies will be introduced (Castellanos, 2008). The second limitation is regarding the expected EOL, given that to all PV types the same alpha and average lifetime parameters are assigned, ignoring the differences between each kind and not considering the shelf life of upcoming technologies, which could be addressed by analyzing the Weibull distributions for all PV types and determining their alpha and T parameters.

On the other hand, the selection of optimal locations could be improved in two ways: by enhancing the optimization model, by evaluating the regulatory aspects inherent to each location. The current location optimization model does not consider downstream flows and actors of the SC, such as locations of raw material demand, which could affect the optimality of location centres. Furthermore, the model only considers the top 12 states with

the highest energy production and discards low-energy production clusters, which could impact the optimal location centres. Additionally, although the model considers spherical distances, it does not account for the actual distances travelled by road between two points, which is the real distance that should be considered for calculating the reverse logistics costs. Lastly, the model does not include the minimum distance from collection points to CCs, which could increase the number of CCs required.

As per the regulatory element, the optimization model, as outlined by Chiquillo-Molano (2022), adeptly identifies cost-effective geographic coordinates for industry development. However, it overlooks the qualitative aspects of potential locations that could either facilitate or impede the growth of the industry within each state. These qualitative factors are crucial for the economic viability of PV recycling, which relies on economies of scale to be sustainable (Vargas & Chesney, 2020; El-Khawad et al., 2022; Iakovou et al., 2024), elements such as incentives and subsidies, extended producer responsibility, recycling targets, and zoning laws. In the context of the United States, only a handful of states generate sufficient waste to support a RC independently. Consequently, it becomes necessary to consolidate waste from multiple states to attain the volume needed for economic feasibility (D'Adamo et al., 2017). This requirement may result in the strategic placement of CCs and RCs at intermediary locations that transcend state borders, potentially involving states with divergent environmental policies. To address this gap, it is imperative to integrate into Chiquillo-Molano's framework a comprehensive methodology that evaluates the mentioned regulatory factors.

5.4. Future direction

Future research should focus on refining the waste forecasting methodology, PV technology forecast, Mathematical optimization models, regulatory analysis, and collaboration in the SC.

Regarding waste forecasting, it is needed is to move beyond basic time series analysis and embrace a multifactorial approach (Zhang et al, 2018; Cabello-López et al, 2023) that utilizes the capabilities of machine learning (Ledmaoui et al, 2023; Al-Ali et al, 2023; Vennila et al, 2022; Basurto et al, 2019) and neural networks (Buturache & Stancu, 2021; Dumitru et al, 2016, Rodríguez et al, 2018). These advanced analytical tools can process complex data sets to identify nuanced patterns in waste generation, incorporating variables such as product life cycles, consumer behaviour, and market trends to yield more accurate predictions.

In tandem with improving waste forecasting, there is a pressing need to develop models for technology forecasting. Such models would predict the emergence of new technologies, along with their EOL, material composition, and the ease with which they can be recycled. This foresight will be crucial for planning future recycling infrastructure and adapting to the rapid pace of technological change.

Enhancing the location optimization process is another critical area for future research. This involves including a wider array of parameters and variables that directly impact the

recycling industry. Factors such as the distance to CCs, actual travel distances, and the presence of downstream demand clusters should be integrated into location optimization models, as outlined in the limitations of the model used in this study. This will ensure that the models more accurately reflect logistical efficiencies and market demands, leading to better-informed decisions about where to site recycling facilities.

Additionally, the adoption of more robust and recent optimization models, such as Hub Location Problem, Hub Network Design Problem, Hub Arc Location Problem (Farahani et al, 2013; Alumur et al, 2021), in addition to stochastic optimization (Sahinidis, 2004), other heuristics and metaheuristics (Tamayo et al, 2015). These models are adept at managing uncertainty in key parameters, such as waste supply, technological evolution, and market conditions. By incorporating stochastic elements, the optimization process can yield solutions that are resilient in the face of various potential future states.

Moreover, it is crucial to address the collaboration between all stakeholders in the SC. Ensuring alignment among the various elements such as new technologies, designs, volumes, and material compositions is essential for the success of recycling initiatives (El-Khawad et al, 2022; Mahmoudi et al, 2019; Iakovou et al, 2024; Vargas & Chesney, 2020; El-Khawad et al, 2022; Radavičius et al, 2021). This collaborative approach requires engagement from manufacturers, consumers, recyclers, policymakers, and other relevant parties. By fostering a collaborative environment, stakeholders can work together to create a cohesive and sustainable recycling SC. This synergy is necessary to address the dynamic nature of waste streams and to adapt to the evolving landscape of materials and technologies. The integration of stakeholder collaboration into the decision-making frameworks will help in building a resilient and future-proof recycling infrastructure.

Finally, it is imperative to include regulatory considerations within the decision-making frameworks for establishing recycling plants. This involves a thorough understanding of the regulatory environment, including incentives, subsidies, extended producer responsibility, recycling targets, and zoning laws. Integrating these regulatory factors ensures that the proposed recycling facilities are not only economically and logistically sound but also in compliance with legal requirements and aligned with government policies. By addressing these regulatory aspects, the frameworks can facilitate the creation of recycling facilities that are both viable and responsible.

Regulatory factors are critical as they can significantly alter the model's outcomes; they are the foundations that can either enable or hinder the practical implementation of the optimized locations for recycling centres. For instance, a model may identify a geographically optimal site for a recycling plant, but if local zoning laws prohibit industrial development in that area, the model's recommendation becomes infeasible. Similarly, if a state offers substantial subsidies or tax incentives for green industries, a location that might otherwise seem less attractive from a purely logistical standpoint could become the most viable option. Extended producer responsibility laws, which require manufacturers to manage the disposal of their products at the end of their life cycle, can also shift the

economic balance, making certain locations more favourable due to the presence of manufacturing facilities.

An example that brings this to life is the case of a recycling facility that might be optimally located near major urban centres to minimize transportation costs from collection points. However, if the urban centre has stringent environmental regulations that limit the processing of materials containing hazardous substances, the facility may need to be located further away, thus increasing transportation costs but ensuring compliance with environmental standards. Another example is the potential impact of recycling targets set by governments, which could necessitate the establishment of multiple smaller facilities across a region to meet distributed recycling quotas, rather than a single, centralized facility that might be indicated by a logistics-only model.

These examples underscore why context is critical and a limitation of modelling. While mathematical models provide a structured approach to identifying optimal solutions, they must be complemented with a detailed understanding of the multifaceted real-world environment in which these solutions will be implemented. Without integrating the full spectrum of regulatory, legal, social, economic, and environmental considerations, the models may yield solutions that are theoretically sound but practically unviable. Therefore, it is essential to approach the modelling process with a holistic perspective that accounts for the dynamic and complex nature of the real world in which recycling facilities will operate.

Chapter 6. Conclusions

This dissertation has made a contribution to the body of knowledge on CE and GSCM by providing a detailed historical perspective and delineating the similarities and differences between these two critical areas and applying their principles to the PV recycling in the US. Through this exploration, the paper has underscored the pressing issue of PV panel waste, which, if not managed appropriately, is poised to become a recurring problem in the coming decades. The research presented confirms the urgent need for effective waste management strategies to address the anticipated surge in PV waste.

A central finding of this study is the confirmation that the application of optimization models can significantly reduce the total reverse logistics costs within a SC. This reduction is pivotal as it directly impacts the economic feasibility of PV recycling, which has been identified as the primary obstacle to recycling efforts. By demonstrating how these costs can be minimized, the paper emphasizes the potential for optimization models to make PV recycling not only environmentally but also economically viable.

However, the identification of optimal locations for recycling infrastructure through mathematical models is only the first step. These frameworks must be evaluated within a broader context that includes regulatory, legal, social, economic, and environmental considerations. The feasibility of establishing capital-intensive recycling operations in the identified locations depends on a complex interplay of these factors. Therefore, a

comprehensive analysis that extends beyond the mathematical optimization is essential to ensure that the proposed solutions are practical and sustainable in real-world scenarios.

While the efficiencies gained through the optimization of SC networks contribute to the economic feasibility of recycling PV panels, it is imperative to recognize that these efforts alone are insufficient. The increase in PV panel recycling rates must be supported by robust policies that not only incentivize proper waste disposal but also create an economic environment conducive to recycling. Policy interventions are crucial in steering the economy towards sustainable practices and ensuring that the industry can thrive while managing PV waste responsibly. Without such policy support, the advancements in SC optimization and the potential economic benefits they bring may not be enough to overcome the challenges facing the PV recycling industry. Therefore, this paper calls for a concerted effort from policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the scientific community to collaborate in creating a regulatory framework that fosters a truly CE for photovoltaic panels.

Glosary of acronyms

PV – Photovoltaic

EOL – End Of Life

RC – Recycling centre

CC- Collection centre

CE- Circular Economy

SC- Supply Chain

RSC – Reverse supply chain

GSCM- Green Supply Chain Management

TQM- Total Quality Management

JIT- Just In Time

CLSCM- Closed Loop Supply Chain Management

RL- Reverse Logistics

RSCM- Reverse Supply Chain Management

SRSCM - Social Risk Supply Chain Management

CSCM- Circular Supply Chain Management

SSCM- Sustainable Supply Chain Management

NPV- Net Present Value

CdTe - Cadmium Telluride

OPV - Organic PVs

CIGS - Copper Indium Gallium Selenide

Appendix

Appendix 1. – Weight-to-power ratio of different PV technologies.

Technology	Kg/W
C-Si	0.103
CIGS	0.157
CdTe	0.185
CPV	0.1
OPV	0.1
Cristaline Si	0.1
Other alternatives	0.1

Source: Chiquillo-Molano (2022)

Appendix 2. – PV technology Market share forecast.

	C-Si	CIGS	CdTe	CPV	OPV	Cristaline Si	Other alternatives
2010	92%	2%	5%	0%	0%	0%	0%
2011	88%	3%	5%	0%	1%	2%	0%
2012	85%	3%	5%	1%	2%	4%	0%
2013	81%	4%	5%	1%	4%	5%	0%
2014	77%	5%	5%	1%	5%	7%	1%
2015	73%	5%	5%	1%	6%	9%	1%
2016	73%	5%	5%	1%	6%	9%	1%
2017	73%	5%	5%	1%	6%	9%	1%
2018	73%	5%	5%	1%	6%	9%	1%
2019	73%	5%	5%	1%	6%	9%	1%
2020	73%	5%	5%	1%	6%	9%	1%
2021	70%	5%	5%	1%	6%	10%	1%
2022	67%	5%	5%	1%	6%	12%	2%
2023	64%	6%	5%	1%	7%	14%	3%
2024	62%	6%	5%	1%	7%	15%	4%
2025	59%	6%	5%	1%	7%	17%	5%
2026	56%	6%	5%	1%	8%	19%	6%
2027	53%	6%	5%	1%	8%	21%	7%
2028	50%	6%	5%	1%	8%	22%	8%
2029	47%	6%	5%	1%	8%	24%	8%
2030	45%	6%	5%	1%	9%	26%	9%
2031	42%	7%	5%	1%	9%	27%	10%
2032	39%	7%	5%	0%	9%	29%	11%
2033	36%	7%	5%	0%	10%	31%	12%
2034	33%	7%	4%	0%	10%	32%	13%
2035	30%	7%	4%	0%	10%	34%	14%
2036	27%	7%	4%	0%	10%	36%	15%
2037	25%	7%	4%	0%	11%	37%	15%
2038	22%	7%	4%	0%	11%	39%	16%
2039	19%	7%	4%	0%	11%	41%	17%
2040	16%	8%	4%	0%	12%	42%	18%

Technology		2014	2020	2030
Silicon-based (c-Si)	Monocrystalline	92%	73.3%	44.8%
	Poly- or multicrystalline			
	Ribbon			
	a-Si (amorph/micromorph)			
Thin-film based	Copper indium gallium (di)selenide (CIGS)	2%	5.2%	6.4%
	Cadmium telluride (CdTe)	5%	5.2%	4.7%
Other	Concentrating solar PV (CPV)	1%	1.2%	0.6%
	Organic PV/dye-sensitised cells (OPV)		5.8%	8.7%
	Crystalline silicon (advanced c-Si)		8.7%	25.6%
	CIGS alternatives, heavy metals (e.g. perovskite), advanced III-V		0.6%	9.3%

Source: Weckend et al. (2017).

Appendix 3. – Solar energy production forecast by state (MW)

	Arizona	California	Colorado	Florida	Georgia	Massachusetts	Nevada	New Jersey	New York	North Carolina	Texas	Virginia
2011	397	887	197	95	7	75	124	700	124	85	86	5
2012	1,106	1,382	300	117	21	207	349	1,033	179	208	140	11
2013	1,563	3,813	360	137	110	445	424	1,253	240	469	216	13
2014	2,069	9,932	400	159	160	734	823	1,458	397	849	387	11
2015	2,303	14,813	544	200	370	1,020	1,240	1,653	638	1,974	594	21
2016	2,943	18,807	921	682	1,470	1,360	2,242	2,061	937	2,984	1,269	217
2017	3,423	24,352	1,019	1,432	1,555	1,699	2,421	2,411	1,038	3,287	1,982	613
2018	3,863	26,986	1,197	2,289	1,568	2,465	2,951	2,738	1,073	4,692	2,925	758
2019	4,646	28,331	1,377	3,690	2,448	2,768	3,556	2,908	1,571	6,152	4,324	898
2020	5,175	30,271	1,708	6,539	2,757	3,046	3,871	3,593	2,724	7,037	7,784	2,311
2021	5,643	34,863	2,183	8,205	4,268	3,607	4,510	3,854	3,381	7,811	13,884	3,761
2022	6,330	39,320	2,995	10,111	5,033	4,158	5,366	4,411	4,259	8,179	17,247	4,286
2023	8,487	48,482	4,168	16,640	5,936	5,233	7,325	5,362	5,834	9,574	32,142	5,418
2024	9,154	52,376	4,502	18,071	6,424	5,651	7,919	5,755	6,315	10,340	34,953	5,873
2025	10,488	60,164	5,170	20,934	7,399	6,488	9,108	6,542	7,278	11,873	40,575	6,782
2026	11,822	67,952	5,838	23,797	8,375	7,324	10,296	7,328	8,240	13,406	46,197	7,691
2027	13,823	79,634	6,840	28,090	9,838	8,578	12,079	8,508	9,684	15,706	54,630	9,055
2028	16,491	95,210	8,176	33,816	11,789	10,251	14,456	10,081	11,609	18,772	65,874	10,873
2029	19,826	114,680	9,845	40,972	14,228	12,342	17,427	12,047	14,015	22,604	79,929	13,146
2030	23,828	138,044	11,849	49,560	17,154	14,851	20,993	14,406	16,902	27,203	96,795	15,874
2031	28,497	165,302	14,187	59,579	20,568	17,778	25,153	17,159	20,271	32,568	116,471	19,056
2032	33,833	196,454	16,859	71,030	24,470	21,124	29,907	20,304	24,121	38,700	138,959	22,693
2033	39,836	231,500	19,864	83,911	28,860	24,887	35,255	23,843	28,452	45,598	164,258	26,784
2034	46,506	270,440	23,204	98,224	33,738	29,069	41,198	27,775	33,264	53,263	192,368	31,330
2035	53,843	313,274	26,877	113,969	39,103	33,669	47,735	32,101	38,558	61,694	223,289	36,331
2036	61,847	360,002	30,885	131,144	44,956	38,687	54,866	36,820	44,332	70,891	257,020	41,786
2037	70,518	410,624	35,226	149,751	51,297	44,123	62,591	41,931	50,588	80,855	293,563	47,696
2038	79,856	465,140	39,902	169,790	58,125	49,978	70,911	47,436	57,325	91,586	332,917	54,060
2039	89,861	523,549	44,911	191,259	65,441	56,250	79,825	53,335	64,544	103,083	375,082	60,879
2040	100,533	585,853	50,255	214,160	73,245	62,941	89,333	59,626	72,243	115,346	420,057	68,153

Appendix 4.-Weighted average of weight-to-power ratio

Year	Silicon-based	CIGS	CdTe	CPV	OPV	Cristaline Si	Other alternatives	Weighted average
2010	0.09476	0.00314	0.00925	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.10815
2011	0.09476	0.00314	0.00925	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.10815
2012	0.09476	0.00314	0.00925	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.10815
2013	0.09476	0.00314	0.00925	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.10815
2014	0.09476	0.00314	0.00925	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.00025	0.10815
2015	0.09155	0.003977	0.009312	0.000408	0.00118	0.001658333	0.00031	0.10838883
2016	0.08834	0.004815	0.009373	0.000567	0.0021	0.003066667	0.00037	0.10862767
2017	0.08513	0.005652	0.009435	0.000725	0.00303	0.004475	0.00043	0.1088665
2018	0.081919	0.006489	0.009497	0.000883	0.00395	0.005883333	0.00048	0.10910533
2019	0.078709	0.007327	0.009558	0.001042	0.00488	0.007291667	0.00054	0.10934417
2020	0.075499	0.008164	0.00962	0.0012	0.0058	0.0087	0.0006	0.109583
2021	0.072254	0.008352	0.009528	0.00114	0.00609	0.01039	0.00147	0.1092244
2022	0.069319	0.008541	0.009435	0.00108	0.00638	0.01208	0.00234	0.1091748
2023	0.066383	0.008729	0.009343	0.00102	0.00667	0.01377	0.00321	0.1091252
2024	0.063448	0.008918	0.00925	0.00096	0.00696	0.01546	0.00408	0.1090756
2025	0.060512	0.009106	0.009158	0.0009	0.00725	0.01715	0.00495	0.109026
2026	0.057577	0.009294	0.009065	0.00084	0.00754	0.01884	0.00582	0.1089764
2027	0.054641	0.009483	0.008973	0.00078	0.00783	0.02053	0.00669	0.1089268
2028	0.051706	0.009671	0.00888	0.00072	0.00812	0.02222	0.00756	0.1088772

Appendix 5. – Latitude and Longitude of optimum locations per scenario

Scenario	Type	Latitude	Longitude
1RC	CC & RC	36.4	-110.2
2RC	CC & RC	37.0	-119.5
	CC & RC	35.9	-78.6
3RC	CC & RC	37.0	-119.5
	CC & RC	35.5	-79.0
	CC & RC	32.7	-103.5
4RC	CC & RC	37.0	-119.5
	CC & RC	40.5	-74.2
	CC & RC	33.7	-80.3
	CC & RC	31.1	-100.3
2DC - 1 RC	CC	37.0	-119.5
	CC	35.9	-78.6
	RC	37.0	-119.5
3DC - 1 RC	CC	37.0	-119.5
	CC	35.5	-79.0
	CC	32.8	-103.4
	RC	32.7	-103.5
4DC - 1 RC	CC	37.0	-119.5
	CC	40.5	-74.2
	CC	33.7	-80.3
	CC	31.1	-100.3
	RC	37.0	-119.5
3DC - 2 RC	CC	37.0	-119.5
	CC	41.4	-74.5
	CC	32.5	-85.6
	RC	37.0	-119.5
	RC	32.5	-85.6
4DC - 2 RC	CC	37.0	-119.5
	CC	40.5	-74.2
	CC	33.7	-80.3
	CC	31.1	-100.3
	RC	37.0	-119.5
	RC	35.3	-83.4
4DC - 3 RC	CC	37.0	-119.5
	CC	40.6	-74.2
	CC	33.6	-80.3
	CC	31.0	-100.0
	RC	37.0	-119.5
	RC	35.4	-78.7
	RC	31.1	-100.3

References:

1. Acharya, A., Ranjan Verma, A. and Bolia, N.B. (2024). Effective collection of end-of-life solar panels through an incentive-based model. *Solar Energy*, [online] 268(112215). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2023.112215>.
2. Agyabeng-Mensah, Y., Afum, E., Agnikpe, C., Cai, J., Ahenkorah, E. and Dacosta, E. (2020). Exploring the mediating influences of total quality management and just in time between green supply chain practices and performance. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 32(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/jmtm-03-2020-0086>.
3. Aityassine, F., Aldiabat, B., Al-rjoub, S., Aldaihani, F., Al-Shorman, H. and Al-Hawary, S. (2021). The mediating effect of just in time on the relationship between green supply chain management practices and performance in the manufacturing companies. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, [online] 9(4), pp.1081–1090. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2021.x.007>.
4. Al-Ali, E.M., Hajji, Y., Said, Y., Hleili, M., Alanzi, A.M., Laatar, A.H. and Atri, M. (2023). Solar Energy Production Forecasting Based on a Hybrid CNN-LSTM-Transformer Model. *Mathematics*, 11(3), p.676. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/math11030676>.
5. Alumur, S.A., Campbell, J.F., Contreras, I., Kara, B.Y., Marianov, V. and O’Kelly, M.E. (2021). Perspectives on modeling hub location problems. *European Journal of Operational Research*, [online] 291(1), pp.1–17. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2020.09.039>.
6. Ayres, R.U. and Kneese, A.V. (1969). Production, Consumption, and Externalities. *The American Economic Review*, [online] 59(3), pp.282–297. Available at: https://www.jstor.org/stable/1808958?saml_data=eyJzYW1sVG9rZW4iOiIwNjcyMjg5Zi03ZmViLTQwNzgtOTEwNS1mOGE2ODAyMzA2OTciLCJpbnN0aXR1dGlvbklkeYl6WyIxMTI1NzY5Yi0xMDZmLTRjYzYtODY1ZS02ZTQ5M2MyZTNiN2MiXX0&seq=6 [Accessed 7 Apr. 2024].
7. Bag, S., Gupta, S. and Kumar, S. (2021). Industry 4.0 adoption and 10R advance

- manufacturing capabilities for sustainable development. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 231(107844), p.107844.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2020.107844>.
8. Bai, C., Sarkis, J., Yin, F. and Dou, Y. (2019). Sustainable supply chain flexibility and its relationship to circular economy-target performance. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(19), pp.1–18.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2019.1661532>.
 9. Basurto, N., Arroyo, Á., Vega, R., Quintián, H., Calvo-Rolle, J.L. and Herrero, Á. (2019). A Hybrid Intelligent System to forecast solar energy production. *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, [online] 78, pp.373–387.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2019.07.023>.
 10. Beamon, B.M. (1999). Designing the green supply chain. *Logistics Information Management*, 12(4), pp.332–342. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/09576059910284159>.
 11. Buturache, A.-N. and Stancu, S. (2021). Solar Energy Production Forecast Using Standard Recurrent Neural Networks, Long Short-Term Memory, and Gated Recurrent Unit. *Engineering Economics*, 32(4), pp.313–324.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.ee.32.4.28459>.
 12. Cabello-López T., Carranza-García, M., Santos and García-Gutiérrez, J. (2023). Forecasting solar energy production in Spain: A comparison of univariate and multivariate models at the national level. *Applied Energy*, 350, pp.121645–121645.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121645>.
 13. Castellanos, O. (2008). Gestion tecnologica: de un enfoque tradicional a la inteligencia. *Universidad Nacional de Colombia. Grupo de investigacion Biogestion*.
 14. Choi, Jun-Ki, and Vasilis Fthenakis. “Crystalline Silicon Photovoltaic Recycling Planning: Macro and Micro Perspectives.” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 66, Mar. 2014, pp. 443–449, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.11.022>.
 15. Chowdhury, Md.S., Rahman, K.S., Chowdhury, T., Nuthammachot, N., Techato, K., Akhtaruzzaman, Md., Tiong, S.K., Sopian, K. and Amin, N. (2020). An overview of solar photovoltaic panels’ end-of-life material recycling. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, [online] 27(27), p.100431.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2019.100431>.

16. COHP. "Extreme Points of the United States." *Www.cohp.org*, www.cohp.org/extremes/extreme_points.html. Accessed 9 July 2024.
17. Corcelli, F., Ripa, M., Leccisi, E., Cigolotti, V., Fiandra, V., Graditi, G., Sannino, L., Tamaro, M. and Ulgiati, S. (2018). Sustainable urban electricity supply chain – Indicators of material recovery and energy savings from crystalline silicon photovoltaic panels end-of-life. *Ecological Indicators*, 94, pp.37–51. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.03.028>.
18. Cunha, L., Ceryno, P. and Leiras, A. (2019). Social supply chain risk management: A taxonomy, a framework and a research agenda. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 220, pp.1101–1110. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.02.183>.
19. D'Adamo, I., Miliacca, M. and Rosa, P. (2017). Economic Feasibility for Recycling of Waste Crystalline Silicon Photovoltaic Modules. *International Journal of Photoenergy*, [online] 2017, pp.1–6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/4184676>.
20. Daniela-Abigail, H.-L., Tariq, R., Mekaoui, A.E., Bassam, A., Vega De Lille, M., J Ricalde, L. and Riech, I. (2022). Does recycling solar panels make this renewable resource sustainable? Evidence supported by environmental, economic, and social dimensions. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 77(103539), p.103539. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2021.103539>.
21. de Oliveira, U.R., Espindola, L.S., da Silva, I.R., da Silva, I.N. and Rocha, H.M. (2018). A systematic literature review on green supply chain management: Research implications and future perspectives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, [online] 187, pp.537–561. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.083>.
22. den Hollander, M.C., Bakker, C.A. and Hultink, E.J. (2017). Product Design in a Circular Economy: Development of a Typology of Key Concepts and Terms. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, [online] 21(3), pp.517–525. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12610>.
23. Divya, A., Adish, T., Kaustubh, P. and Zade, P.S. (2023). Review on recycling of solar modules/panels. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 253(112151). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2022.112151>.
24. Dumitru, C.-D., Gligor, A. and Enachescu, C. (2016). Solar Photovoltaic Energy

- Production Forecast Using Neural Networks. *Procedia Technology*, 22, pp.808–815. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.protcy.2016.01.053>.
25. EIA (2021). “Narrative - U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA).” *Www.eia.gov*, 16 Mar. 2023, www.eia.gov/outlooks/aeo/narrative/. Accessed 9 July 2024.
26. EIA (2023). “EIA Projects Renewables Share of U.S. Electricity Generation Mix Will Double by 2050 - U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA).” *Www.eia.gov*, 2021, [www.eia.gov/todayinenergy/detail.php?id=46676#:~:text=Solar%20electric%20generation%20\(which%20includes](http://www.eia.gov/todayinenergy/detail.php?id=46676#:~:text=Solar%20electric%20generation%20(which%20includes). Accessed 10 July 2024.
27. Ekins, P., Domenech, T., Drummond, P., Bleischwitz, R., Hughes, N. and Lotti, L. (2019). *The Circular Economy: What, Why, How and Where*. [online] Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/cfe/regionaldevelopment/Ekins-2019-Circular-Economy-What-Why-How-Where.pdf> [Accessed 7 Apr. 2024].
28. Eleftherios Iakovou, Pistikopoulos, E.N., Julien Walzberg, Iseri, F., Iseri, H., Chrisandina, N.J., Shivam Vedant and Nkoutche, C. (2024). Next-generation reverse logistics networks of photovoltaic recycling: Perspectives and challenges. *Solar Energy*, 271(112329). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2024.112329>.
29. El-Khawad, L., Bartkowiak, D. and Kümmerer, K. (2022). Improving the end-of-life management of solar panels in Germany. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 168(112678). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112678>.
30. Fahimnia, B., Sarkis, J. and Davarzani, H. (2015). Green supply chain management: A review and bibliometric analysis. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 162, pp.101–114. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2015.01.003>.
31. Farahani, R.Z., Hekmatfar, M., Arabani, A.B. and Nikbakhsh, E. (2013). Hub location problems: A review of models, classification, solution techniques, and applications. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 64(4), pp.1096–1109. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2013.01.012>.
32. Farooque, M., Zhang, A., Thürer, M., Qu, T. and Huisingh, D. (2019). Circular supply chain management: A definition and structured literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 228, pp.882–900.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.303>.

33. Franco, M.A. and Groesser, S.N. (2021). A Systematic Literature Review of the Solar Photovoltaic Value Chain for a Circular Economy. *Sustainability*, 13(17). doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13179615>.
34. Frosch, R.A. and Gallopoulos, N.E. (1989). Strategies for Manufacturing. *Scientific American*, [online] 261(3), pp.144–153. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24987406> [Accessed 7 Apr. 2024].
35. Fthenakis, V. M., Eberspacher, C., & Moskowitz, P. D. (1996). Recycling strategies to enhance the commercial viability of CIS photovoltaics. *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, 4(6), 447-456. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-159X\(199611/12\)4:6<447::AID-PIP147>3.0.CO;2-F](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-159X(199611/12)4:6<447::AID-PIP147>3.0.CO;2-F)
36. Fthenakis, V.M. (2000). End-of-life management and recycling of PV modules. *Energy Policy*, 28(14), pp.1051–1058. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0301-4215\(00\)00091-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0301-4215(00)00091-4).
37. Gamboa Bernal, J.P., Orjuela Castro, J.A. and Moreno Mantilla, C.E. (2020). The Sustainable Supply Chain: Concepts, Optimization and Simulation Models, and Trends. *Ingeniería*, [online] 25(3), pp.355–377. doi:<https://doi.org/10.14483/23448393.16926>.
38. Gautam, A., Shankar, R. and Vrat, P. (2021). End-of-life solar photovoltaic e-waste assessment in India: a step towards a circular economy. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 26, pp.65–77. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2020.09.011>.
39. Genovese, A., Acquaye, A.A., Figueroa, A. and Koh, S.C.L. (2017). Sustainable Supply Chain Management and the Transition Towards a Circular economy: Evidence and Some Applications. *Omega*, [online] 66(B), pp.344–357. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2015.05.015>.
40. Gönen, Ç. and Kaplanoğlu, E. (2019). Environmental and economic evaluation of solar panel wastes recycling. *Waste Management & Research: The Journal for a Sustainable Circular Economy*, 37(4), pp.412–418. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242x19826331>.
41. Green, K.W., Inman, R.A., Sower, V.E. and Zelbst, P.J. (2019a). Comprehensive supply chain management model. *Supply Chain Management: An International*

- Journal*, 24(5). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/scm-12-2018-0441>.
42. Green, K.W., Inman, R.A., Sower, V.E. and Zelbst, P.J. (2019b). Impact of JIT, TQM and green supply chain practices on environmental sustainability. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 30(1), pp.26–47.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/jmtm-01-2018-0015>.
43. Guide, V.D.R. and Van Wassenhove, L.N. (2009). The Evolution of Closed-Loop Supply Chain Research. *Operations Research*, 57(1), pp.10–18.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1287/opre.1080.0628>.
44. Heath, G.A., Ravikumar, D., Hansen, B. and Kupets, E. (2022). A critical review of the circular economy for lithium-ion batteries and photovoltaic modules – status, challenges, and opportunities. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association*, 72(6), pp.478–539. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/10962247.2022.2068878>.
45. Homrich, A.S., Galvão, G., Abadia, L.G. and Carvalho, M.M. (2018). The circular economy umbrella: Trends and gaps on integrating pathways. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 175, pp.525–543. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.11.064>.
46. Jayaraman, V., Guide, V.D.R. and Srivastava, R. (1999). A closed-loop logistics model for remanufacturing. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 50(5), pp.497–508. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.jors.2600716>.
47. Jermsittiparsert, K., Namdej, P. and Somjai, S. (2019). Green Supply Chain Practices and Sustainable Performance: Moderating Role of Total Quality Management Practices in Electronic Industry of Thailand. *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*, [online] 8(3), pp.33–46. Available at: <https://ojs.excelingtech.co.uk/index.php/IJSCM/article/view/3247> [Accessed 2 Jun. 2024].
48. Kirchherr, J., Reike, D. and Hekkert, M. (2017). Conceptualizing the circular economy: an analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 127, pp.221–232. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.09.005>.
49. Korhonen, J., Honkasalo, A. and Seppälä, J. (2018). Circular Economy: the Concept and Its Limitations. *Ecological Economics*, [online] 143(1), pp.37–46.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.06.041>.
50. Krikke, H., Blanc, I. le and van de Velde, S. (2004). Product Modularity and the

- Design of Closed-Loop Supply Chains. *California Management Review*, 46(2), pp.23–39. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2307/41166208>.
51. Lee, S.-H. and Jang, Y.-C. (2023). Analysis for End-of-Life Solar Panel Generations by Renewable Energy Supply towards Carbon Neutrality in South Korea. *Energies*, 16(24), pp.8039–8039. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/en16248039>.
 52. Lienig, J. and Bruemmer, H. (2017). Recycling Requirements and Design for Environmental Compliance. *Fundamentals of Electronic Systems Design*, [online] pp.193–218. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-55840-0_7.
 53. Liu, J., Feng, Y., Zhu, Q. and Sarkis, J. (2018). Green supply chain management and the circular economy. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 48(8), pp.794–817. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/ijpdlm-01-2017-0049>.
 54. Londoño D.C., Narváez P.A., López J.M., (2015). Optimal location and sizing of distributed generation : a review of the state of the art. *Universidad de Antioquia*. [online] doi:<https://doi.org/1900-2351>.
 55. Lowe, E. (1993). Industrial ecology—an organizing framework for environmental management. *Environmental Quality Management*, 3(1), pp.73–85. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/tqem.3310030108>.
 56. Mahmoudi, S., Huda, N. and Behnia, M. (2021). Critical assessment of renewable energy waste generation in OECD countries: Decommissioned PV panels. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 164, p.105145. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105145>.
 57. Makhlouf, H., Chatti, N. and Lakhal, L. (2023). The impact of TQM and green innovation on corporate sustainability: the mediating role of green supply chain management. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 40(10). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/ijqrm-10-2022-0291>.
 58. Malviya, R.K. and Kant, R. (2015). Green supply chain management (GSCM): a structured literature review and research implications. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 22(7), pp.1360–1394. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/bij-01-2014-0001>.
 59. MIT (2015). *Key Concepts: Week 2 Lesson 1: Introduction to Demand Forecasting*

- . Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2015.
60. Molano, J.C., Xing, K., Majewski, P. and Huang, B. (2022). A holistic reverse logistics planning framework for end-of-life PV panel collection system design. *Journal of Environmental Management*, [online] 317(115331), p.115331. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115331>.
 61. Moreno, M., De los Rios, C., Rowe, Z. and Charnley, F. (2016). A Conceptual Framework for Circular Design. *Sustainability*, 8(9), p.937. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su8090937>.
 62. Narasimhan, R. and Carter, J.R. (1998). *Environmental Supply Chain Management*. Google Books. Centre for Advanced Purchasing Studies.
 63. Pearce, D. and R. Turner (1990), *Economics of Natural Resources and the Environment*, Harvester Wheatsheaf, Hemel Hempstead, Herts., UK.
 64. Peplow, M. (2022). Solar Panels Face Recycling Challenge. *ACS Central Science*, pp.299–302. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1021/acscentsci.2c00214>.
 65. Perez-Franco, R., Caplice C., Singh, M., and Sheffi, Y. (2014) Expressing a supply-chain strategy as a conceptual system. *Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Engineering Systems Division*. [Online] <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/103008>
 66. Plaza-Úbeda, J.A., Abad-Segura, E., de Burgos-Jiménez, J., Boteva-Asenova, A. and Belmonte-Ureña, L.J. (2020). Trends and New Challenges in the Green Supply Chain: The Reverse Logistics. *Sustainability*, 13(1), p.331. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13010331>.
 67. Rabaia, M.K.H., Semeraro, C. and Olabi, A.-G. (2022). Recent progress towards photovoltaics' circular economy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 373(133864). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133864>.
 68. Radavičius, T., van der Heide, A., Palitzsch, W., Rommens, T., Denafas, J., Tvaronavičienė, M. 2021. Circular solar industry supply chain through product technological design changes. *Insights into Regional Development*, 3(3), 10-30. [http://doi.org/10.9770/IRD.2021.3.3\(1\)](http://doi.org/10.9770/IRD.2021.3.3(1))
 69. Rathore, P., Kota, S. and Chakrabarti, A. (2011). Sustainability through remanufacturing in India: a case study on mobile handsets. *Journal of Cleaner*

Production, 19(15), pp.1709–1722.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.06.016>.

70. Rodríguez, F., Fleetwood, A., Galarza, A. and Fontán, L. (2018). Predicting solar energy generation through artificial neural networks using weather forecasts for microgrid control. *Renewable Energy*, 126, pp.855–864.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.03.070>.
71. Sahinidis, N.V. (2004). Optimization under uncertainty: state-of-the-art and opportunities. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 28(6-7), pp.971–983.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2003.09.017>.
72. Sangpech, P. and Ueasangkomsate, P. (2022). Supply Chain Management and the Circular Economy: A Review of Current Research and Future Trends. *2022 Joint International Conference on Digital Arts, Media and Technology with ECTI Northern Section Conference on Electrical, Electronics, Computer and Telecommunications Engineering (ECTI DAMT & NCON)*.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/ectidamtncon53731.2022.9720414>.
73. Santos, J.D. and Alonso-García, M.C. (2018). Projection of the photovoltaic waste in Spain until 2050. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 196, pp.1613–1628.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.05.252>.
74. Sarkis, J. and Rasheed, A. (1995). Greening the manufacturing function. *Business Horizons*, 38(5), pp.17–27. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0007-6813\(00\)2895\)90032-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0007-6813(00)2895)90032-2).
75. Sarkis, J., Zhu, Q. and Lai, K. (2011). An organizational theoretic review of green supply chain management literature. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 130(1), pp.1–15. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2010.11.010>.
76. Sarkis, Joseph. (1995). Supply Chain Management and Environmentally Conscious Design and Manufacturing. *International Journal of Environmentally Conscious Design and Manufacturing*. 4. 43-52.
77. Saunders M., Lewis P., and Thornhill A. (2020). Research Methods for Business Students. *Pearson*. Eight edition.
78. Scale Funding. “Current Freight Rates.” *Scale Funding*, June 2024, getscalefunding.com/resources/current-freight-rates/. Accessed 9 July 2024.
79. SEIA (2024). “State-By-State Map | SEIA.” *SEIA*, www.seia.org/states-map.

[Accessed 9 July 2024.](#)

80. Seuring, S. and Müller, M. (2008). From a Literature Review to a Conceptual Framework for Sustainable Supply Chain Management. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 16(15), pp.1699–1710.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2008.04.020>.
81. Sharma, A., Mahajan, P. and Garg, R. (2023). End-of-life solar photovoltaic panel waste management in India: forecasting and environmental impact assessment. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, [online] 21.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-023-04953-2>.
82. Sillanpää, M. and Ncibi, C. (2019). Getting hold of the circular economy concept. *The Circular Economy*, pp.1–35. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-815267-6.00001-3>.
83. Silvério, A.C., Ferreira, J., Fernandes, P.O. and Dabić, M. (2023). How does circular economy work in industry? Strategies, opportunities, and trends in scholarly literature. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 412(137312), p.137312.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137312>.
84. Singh, A. and Trivedi, A. (2016). Sustainable green supply chain management: trends and current practices. *Competitiveness Review*, 26(3), pp.265–288.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/cr-05-2015-0034>.
85. Soltanmohammadi, A., Ardakani, D.A., Dion, P.A. and Hettiarachchi, B.D. (2021). Employing Total Quality Practices in Sustainable Supply Chain Management. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 28.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.07.013>.
86. Srivastava, S.K. (2007). Green supply-chain management: A state-of-the-art literature review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 9(1), pp.53–80.
87. Statista (2016). *Forecasted cumulative solar PV panel waste globally by key country 2050*. [online] Statista. Available at:
<https://www.statista.com/statistics/565643/solar-pv-panels-waste-projection-by-major-country-globally/>.
88. Tanveer, M., Khan, S.A.R., Umar, M., Yu, Z., Sajid, M.J. and Haq, I.U. (2022). Waste management and green technology: future trends in circular economy leading

- towards environmental sustainability. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(53), pp.80161–80178. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-23238-8>.
89. Tao, M., Fthenakis, V., Ebin, B., Steenari, B., Butler, E., Sinha, P., Corkish, R., Wambach, K. and Simon, E.S. (2020). Major challenges and opportunities in silicon solar module recycling. *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, 28(10), pp.1077–1088. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.3316>.
90. Thieu, T.Q., Le, A.K.H., Pham, M.T., Phuc, P.N.K. and Tran, V.H. (2022). A Reverse Supply Chain Model to Reduce Waste of Solar Panel in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. *Journal of Advanced Engineering and Computation*, [online] 6(2), pp.136–152. Available at: <https://jaec.vn/index.php/JAEC/article/view/354/178> [Accessed 7 Apr. 2024].
91. Tseng, M.-L., Islam, M.S., Karia, N., Fauzi, F.A. and Afrin, S. (2019). A literature review on green supply chain management: Trends and future challenges. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, [online] 141(1), pp.145–162. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.10.009>.
92. van Hoek, R.I. (1999). From reversed logistics to green supply chains. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 4(3), pp.129–135. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/13598549910279576>.
93. Vargas, C. and Chesney, M. (2020). End of life decommissioning and recycling of solar panels in the United States. A real options analysis. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, pp.82–102. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/20430795.2019.1700723>.
94. Weckend, S., Wade, A. and Heath, G.A. (ORCID:0000000160104475) (2016). *End of Life Management: Solar Photovoltaic Panels*. [online] www.osti.gov. Available at: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1561525> [Accessed 2 Jun. 2024].
95. Xu, Y., Li, J., Tan, Q., Peters, A.L. and Yang, C. (2018). Global status of recycling waste solar panels: A review. *Waste Management*, [online] 75, pp.450–458. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.01.036>.
96. You, F., Tao, L., Graziano, D.J. and Snyder, S.W. (2011). Optimal design of sustainable cellulosic biofuel supply chains: Multiobjective optimization coupled

- with life cycle assessment and input-output analysis. *AIChE Journal*, 58(4), pp.1157–1180. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.12637>.
97. Younes Ledmaoui, Adila El Maghraoui, Mohamed El Aroussi, Rachid Saadane, Chebak, A. and Abdellah Chehri (2023). Forecasting solar energy production: A comparative study of machine learning algorithms. *Energy Reports*, 10, pp.1004–1012. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2023.07.042>.
98. Yue, D., Kim, M.A. and You, F. (2013). Design of Sustainable Product Systems and Supply Chains with Life Cycle Optimization Based on Functional Unit: General Modeling Framework, Mixed-Integer Nonlinear Programming Algorithms and Case Study on Hydrocarbon Biofuels. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 1(8), pp.1003–1014. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1021/sc400080x>.
99. Zahran, S. (2024). Investigating the Nexus between Green Supply Chain Practices and Sustainable Waste Management in Advancing Circular Economy. *Sustainability*, [online] 16(9), p.3566. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su16093566>.
100. Zaid, A.A. and Sleimi, M. (2021). Effect of total quality management on business sustainability: the mediating role of green supply chain management practices. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 66(3), pp.1–25. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2021.1997730>.
101. Zhang, R., Feng, M., Zhang, W., Lu, S. and Wang, F. (2018). Forecast of Solar Energy Production - A Deep Learning Approach. *2018 IEEE International conference*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/icbk.2018.00018>.
102. Zhu, Q., Sarkis, J. and Lai, K. (2008). Green supply chain management implications for ‘closing the loop’. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, [online] 44(1), pp.1–18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2006.06.003>.